

Thesis for the Degree of Master of Science in Construction
Management

**Risk Management Practice adopted in Road
Construction in perspective of COVID-19**

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(2019-1-06-0020)

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Urlabari -3, Morang

September, 2021

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Supervised by Assoc. Prof. Anjay Kumar Mishra, Ph.D.

A thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the
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Declaration

I hereby declare that this study entitled “**Risk Management Practice adopted in Road Construction in perspective of COVID-19**” is based on my original research work. Related works on the topic by other researchers have been duly acknowledged. I owe all the liabilities relating to the accuracy and authenticity of the data and any other information included hereunder.

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Recommendation

This is to certify that this thesis entitled “**Risk Management Practice adopted in Road Construction in perspective of COVID-19**” prepared and submitted by **Hemant Gain**, in partial fulfillment of the requirements of the degree of Master of Science (M.Sc.) in Construction Management awarded by Pokhara University, has been completed under my supervision. I recommend the same for acceptance by Pokhara University.

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This thesis entitled “**Risk Management Practice adopted in Road Construction in perspective of COVID-19**” prepared and submitted by **Hemant Gain** has been examined by us and is accepted for the award of the degree of Master of Science (M.Sc.) in Construction Management by Pokhara University.

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Abstract

Risk management is defined as process of identification of risk factors, their assessment as well as prioritization of risks along with economical application of resources to minimize and control the occurrence of the risk events. The overall aim of this study is to analyze the practice of risk management along with its impact in road construction in Sindhupalchowk district with the perspective of global pandemic of coronavirus disease (COVID-19).

This research is conducted through questionnaire survey to collect the primary data. Response obtained from respondents is rated on a 5 point Likert scale and analyzed through MS Excel. Risk Management Practice is documented based on survey response in percentage through charts and graphs. The data are analyzed to find out mean and ranking of each risk factors for the severity of risk based on FMEA model regarding their probability of occurrence, its consequence and its detectability. The output regarding the impact is achieved through hypothesis testing using regression analysis between the three independent variables i.e. risk identification, assessment and response and ten success criteria obtained through top ten risk factors.

The results from this research indicates that contractor's organization are averagely aware with a mean score of 3.30 about Risk Management Practice and averagely practicing risk management formally with mean score of 2.83. They are averagely analyzing risk management techniques with mean score of 3.07. Mean score is slightly higher based on client's perspective with score for awareness being 3.93 and score for risk management being practiced formally is 3.13. Risk analysis score based on client's management is 3.40. Mostly adopted technique of risk identification is monitoring and evaluation report of similar past projects and direct judgment is widely used technique for risk assessment of road construction projects at Sindhupalchowk district based on both client's and contractor's perspective. Risk response strategy based on contractor's perspective is monitoring the risk and preparing contingency plan whereas that for client is transfer of risk.

Major risk factors based on risk priority number are time overrun risk, Safety Health and Environmental risk, cost overrun risk, financial and economic risk, force majeure and ecological risk, political legal and social risk, organizational risk, contractual risk, quality risk and design and specification risk in descending order of risk severity. Similarly, it is found that risk management practice has significant impact on nine out of ten success criteria. Risk Identification and Assessment is found to have no impact on project within estimated budget however Risk Response strategy has significant impact on project within estimated budget criteria.

Keywords: Risk Management Practice, Risk Occurrence, Risk Consequences, Risk Detectability, FMEA, Risk Identification, Risk Assessment, Risk Response.

Table of Content

Declaration	i
Recommendation.....	ii
Certificate	iii
Acknowledgements	iv
Abstract	v
Table of Content.....	v
List of Table	ix
List of Figures	xiii
List of Appendix	xiv
List of Abbreviation/Acronyms	xv

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background	1
1.2 Statement of the Problem	2
1.3 Research Questions	3
1.4 Research Objectives	3
1.5 Significance of the Study	4
1.6 Scope and Limitations of the Study	4

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review.....	5
2.1.1 Risk and Uncertainty.....	5
2.1.2 Sources of Risk	5
2.1.3 Typical Risk in a Construction Project	6

2.1.4	Risk Management Process	6
2.2	Empirical Review on Risk Management	9
2.2.1	Global Practice of Risk Management	9
2.2.2	Regional Practice of Risk Management	10
2.2.3	Risk Management Practice in Nepal	11
2.2.4	FEMA Model	12
2.2.5	Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19)	12

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

3.1	Research Flow Process	14
3.2	Study Area	15
3.3	Study Population	17
3.4	Sampling Method	17
3.5	Sample Size	17
3.6	Data Collection	17
3.6.1	Primary Data	17
3.6.2	Secondary Data	19
3.7	Data Analysis	19
3.8	Expected Result	23
3.9	Summary of Methodology	24

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1	Risk Management Practice	25
4.1.1	Risk Management Practice, Contractor's Perspective	25
4.1.2	Risk Management Practice, Client's Perspective	31
4.2	Conformance to Quality Standards	36
4.2.1	Gradation of Base Material	37
4.2.2	Gradation of Premix Chips	38
4.2.3	Los Angeles Abrasion Test	40
4.2.4	Aggregate Impact Test	42
4.2.5	Core Cutting of Premix Surface	44

4.3	Significant Risk Factors and their Ranking based on Failure Mode and Effect Analysis	45
4.4	Impact of Risk Management Practice on Project Success Criteria	50

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1	Conclusion.....	55
5.2	Recommendation.....	56
5.3	Proposed future studies	57
	REFERENCES.....	58
	APPENDICES	61
	APPENDIX I.....	62
	APPENDIX II	71
	APPENDIX III.....	73
	APPENDIX IV	79
	APPENDIX V	82

List of Table

Table 2.1 Various Risk Analysis Technique.....	8
Table 3.1 Research Matrix	24
Table 4.1 Management Awareness Regarding Risk Management, Contractor’s Perspective	25
Table 4.2 Management Practicing Risk Management Formally or Informally, Contractor’s Perspective	26
Table 4.3 Management Practicing Risk Management Formally, Contractor’s Perspective	27
Table 4.4 Management Analyzing Various Risk Management Techniques, Contractor’s Perspective	28
Table 4.5 Reliability Statistics for Risk Management Practice, Contractor’s Perspective .	31
Table 4.6 Management Awareness Regarding Risk Management, Client’s Perspective ...	31
Table 4.7 Management Practicing Risk Management Formally or Informally, Client’s Perspective	32
Table 4.8 Management Practicing Risk Management Formally, Client’s Perspective.....	33
Table 4.9 Management Analyzing Various Risk Management Techniques, Client’s Perspective	33
Table 4.10 Reliability Statistics for Risk Management Practice, Client’s Perspective	36
Table 4.11 Sieve Analysis Report of Base Material	37
Table 4.12 Gradation of Aggregate for Premix of Sample A	38
Table 4.13 Gradation of Aggregate for Premix of Sample B	39
Table 4.14 Los Angeles Abrasion Test for Sample A	40
Table 4.15 Los Angeles Abrasion Test for Sample B.....	40
Table 4.16 Los Angeles Abrasion Test for Sample C.....	41
Table 4.17 Chi Square Hypothesis Testing for LLA Value.....	41
Table 4.18 Aggregate Impact Value for Sample A.....	42

Table 4.19 Aggregate Impact Value for Sample B	42
Table 4.20 Aggregate Impact Value for Sample C	43
Table 4.21 Chi Square Hypothesis Testing for Aggregate Impact Value.....	43
Table 4.22 Core Cutting of Premix Surface at Site A.....	44
Table 4.23 Core Cutting of Premix Surface at Site B	45
Table 4.24 FMEA Table for the Risk Factors.....	46
Table 4.25 Risk Ranking of the Risk Factors	47
Table 4.26 Reliability Statistics for Significant Risk Factor.....	49
Table 4.27 Impact of Risk Identification on Project Success	50
Table 4.28 Impact of Risk Assessment on Project Success	51
Table 4.29 Impact of Risk Response on Project Success.....	51
Table 4.30 Reliability Statistics for Impact on Project Success Criteria	54
Table 6.1 Linguistic Definition for Numerical Rating.....	64
Table 6.2 Risk Factors.....	65
Table 6.3 Project Success Criteria	70
Table 6.4 Response related to Risk Management Practice, Contractor’s Perspective.....	71
Table 6.5 Response related to Risk Management Practice, Client’s Perspective	72
Table 6.6 Average Response for Risk Occurrence of the Risk Factors	73
Table 6.7 Average Response for Risk Consequences of the Risk Factors.....	75
Table 6.8 Average Response for Risk Detectability of the Risk Factors.....	77
Table 6.9 Response Related to Impact of Risk Identification on Project Success Criteria	79
Table 6.10 Response Related to Impact of Risk Assessment on Project Success Criteria	.80
Table 6.11 Response Related to Impact of Risk Response on Project Success Criteria.....	81
Table 6.12 Regression to find impact of Risk Identification on well planned project schedule.....	82
Table 6.13 Regression to find impact of Risk Identification on compliance with Safety, Health and Environmental Standards.....	83

Table 6.14 Regression to find impact of Risk Identification on Project within the Estimated Budget	83
Table 6.15 Regression to find impact of Risk Identification on well assured Financial and Economic Provisions.....	84
Table 6.16 Regression to find impact of Risk Identification on Provision made for Force Majeure Situation	85
Table 6.17 Regression to find impact of Risk Identification on compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements.....	86
Table 6.18 Regression to find impact of Risk Identification on well-structured Organizational Management	86
Table 6.19 Regression to find impact of Risk Identification on No issue in Contractual Arrangement.....	87
Table 6.20 Regression to find impact of Risk Identification on compliance with the Quality Standards	88
Table 6.21 Regression to find impact of Risk Identification on compliance with Technical Design Requirements	89
Table 6.22 Regression to find impact of Risk Assessment on well planned project schedule	89
Table 6.23 Regression to find impact of Risk Assessment on compliance with Safety, Health and Environmental Standards.....	90
Table 6.24 Regression to find impact of Risk Assessment on Project within the Estimated Budget	91
Table 6.25 Regression to find impact of Risk Assessment on well assured Financial and Economic Provisions.....	92
Table 6.26 Regression to find impact of Risk Assessment on Provision made for Force Majeure Situation	92
Table 6.27 Regression to find impact of Risk Assessment on compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements.....	93
Table 6.28 Regression to find impact of Risk Assessment on well-structured Organizational Management	94

Table 6.29 Regression to find impact of Risk Assessment on No issue in Contractual Arrangement.....	95
Table 6.30 Regression to find impact of Risk Assessment on compliance with the Quality Standards	95
Table 6.31 Regression to find impact of Risk Assessment on compliance with Technical Design Requirements	96
Table 6.32 Regression to find impact of Risk Response on well planned project schedule	97
Table 6.33 Regression to find impact of Risk Response on compliance with Safety, Health and Environmental Standards	98
Table 6.34 Regression to find impact of Risk Response on Project within the Estimated Budget	98
Table 6.35 Regression to find impact of Risk Response on well assured Financial and Economic Provisions.....	99
Table 6.36 Regression to find impact of Risk Response on Provision made for Force Majeure Situation	100
Table 6.37 Regression to find impact of Risk Response on compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements.....	101
Table 6.38 Regression to find impact of Risk Response on well-structured Organizational Management.....	101
Table 6.39 Regression to find impact of Risk Response on No issue in Contractual Arrangement.....	102
Table 6.40 Regression to find impact of Risk Response on compliance with the Quality Standards	103
Table 6.41 Regression to find impact of Risk Response on compliance with Technical Design Requirements	104

List of Figures

Fig. 2.1 Flowchart of Risk Management Process	7
Fig. 3.1 Methodological Framework.....	14
Fig. 3.2 Landslide Susceptibility of Sindhupalchowk District	15
Fig. 3.3 Road Network Map of Sindhupalchowk District	16
Fig. 3.4 Research Model for Hypothesis Testing.....	22
Fig. 4.1 Comparative use of Risk Identification Techniques, Contractor’s Perspective	29
Fig. 4.2 Comparative use of Risk Analysis Techniques, Contractor’s Perspective	29
Fig. 4.3 Comparative use of Risk Response Strategy, Contractor’s Perspective.....	30
Fig. 4.4 Comparative use of Risk Identification Techniques, Client’s Perspective.....	34
Fig. 4.5 Comparative use of Risk Analysis Techniques, Client’s Perspective	35
Fig. 4.6 Comparative use of Risk Response Strategy, Client’s Perspective	36
Fig. 4.7 Particle Size Distribution Curve	37
Fig. 4.8 Premix Particle Size Distribution Curve for Sample A	38
Fig. 4.9 Premix Particle Size Distribution Curve for Sample B	39
Fig 4.10 Weightage of Project Risk Factors	49

List of Appendix

Appendix I	Questionnaire Survey Form
Appendix II	Response Related to Risk Management Practice
Appendix III	Response Related to FMEA Model
Appendix IV	Response Related to Project Success Criteria
Appendix V	Hypothesis Analysis

List of Abbreviation/Acronyms

COVID-19	Corona virus Disease
FMEA	Failure Mode and Effect Analysis
IDO	Infrastructure Development Office
ISO	International Organization Standardization
NIST	National Institute of Standard and Technology
PMI	Project Management Institute
PMBOK	Project Management Body of Knowledge
RC	Risk Consequence
RCI	Risk Consequence Index
RD	Risk Detectability
RDI	Risk Detectability Index
RO	Risk Occurrence
ROI	Risk Occurrence Index
RPN	Risk Priority Number
WHO	World Health Organization

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Risk management is defined as process of identification of risk factors, their assessment as well as prioritization of risks along with economical application of resources to minimize and control the occurrence of the risk events. Risk management activities is set of coordinated activities that directs an organization in response to the risk events (ISO 31000). The main goal of risk management is to ensure that uncertainties do not deviate the project as per planned output.

Risk management is an ongoing process that allows the project manager to take control of project throughout its life cycle and be prepared for the unseen problems that might occur at any point of project life. Project team needs to establish standard risk management practice from its earliest phase that helps in proper and timely identification of risk and deal with it in an efficient manner. (Petrovic, 2017). This facilitates in clearer understanding of potential risk factors associated with project, detail assessment methods and appropriate response strategy. It also helps to establish well documented historical record that serves as a reference for evaluating future projects.

Risk can be categorized based on its nature, occurrence, severity and many other purposes. Different authors have classified risks based on different categories. PMI (2009) has categorized risk into two broad categories as internal and external risks. As per Aleshin (2001), risk is categorized into numerous categories like market risk, financial risk, political risk, social risk, intellectual property risk and safety risk. Similarly, Ahmed & Dikbas (2013) have categorized risk based on project being local level or international level. The internal risk depends within the constraints of project and is independent of project being local or international level where as external risk depends upon the environment where the project is being constructed and depends on political scenario, social environment, applicable regulations, legal authorities and procedural formalities.

Risk can come from various sources like possibility of project failures at any phase of project life cycle as in planning & design phase, construction & development, operation and sustainment of life cycle, legal boundaries, financial risk, accidents, force majeure conditions, uncertain events and unforeseen conditions. Standard risk management practice has been developed by various institutions like Project Management Institute (PMI), ISO Standard, National Institute of Standard and Technology (NIST) and Actuarial Societies.

Failure Mode & Effect Analysis (FMEA) is a structured technique which is recognized as one of the most suitable technique to analyze risk factors. FMEA technique was developed by reliability engineers of U.S.A for their army works. But now it is used in several industrial and research fields. In this analysis, each risk is considered as failure mode. Here, risks are prioritized on the basis of Risk Priority Number (RPN). RPN is multiplication of occurrence, consequence and detectability of risk. A risk having higher RPN than others

means that it has higher severity and requires more attention for responses than others (Sharma & Trivedi, 2019).

Risk has mainly three components, Occurrence (O), Consequence (C) and Detectability (D). RPN is function of O, C & D i.e.

$RPN = O \times C \times D$ and

Risk Occurrence (RO) refers to probability of occurrence of risk factor.

Risk Consequence (RC) refers to impact of occurred risk on objectives of project.

Risk Detectability (RD) refers to likelihood of discovering and correcting a risk event prior to harm occurrence.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The projects belonging to construction industry is characterized as fragmented and complex activities and procedures that possibly brings upon huge risk exposure. Project team needs real time and reliable information regarding project environment for proper identification of risk and consider systematic approach for risk response strategy. Selection of appropriate risk management standards is very essential to manage risk associated with the project and ensure successful completion of project within its desired quality.

Nepal being a landlocked country, road construction as a major mode of transportation is always a matter of utmost importance. After the federalism in Nepal, there are lots of infrastructure works going on rapid pace in all parts of the country. From the entire infrastructure works, construction of the road is very essential for development of the country. The success of these roads projects determine growth and development of area resulting into overall development of the nation. So, to ensure success of these projects, risk management should be effectively implemented resulting into successful development of a community.

The coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic has become a global challenge for current economy and has huge impact on human life, their society and the global economy as a whole. The characteristics of COVID-19 pandemic has created uncertainty in control over the spread. It is very contagious and challenging to control its spread. Few studies even show that infected people can be asymptomatic as well, limiting the control of COVID-19 through expansion of testing and isolating capacities. It is not known how long vaccine immunity reliably lasts, thus multiple-wave cannot be ignored for long time. The need to comply with social distancing limits the efficiency of construction works on sites. Under such circumstances, to carry out construction activity as well as ensure safe working environment with effective risk management strategy is a big challenge worldwide.

Risk management determines success and failure of the project. In Nepal, most of the construction company does not make any risk management teamwork before the startup of the construction project. The common practice of risk management is thumb method, common sense, sharp judgment and trial and error method which cannot be considered as scientific method of risk management. So, the aim of this study is to analyze the practice of risk management, various risk factors and its impact in road construction project of Sindhupalchowk district, Province 3, Nepal along with COVID-19 perspective.

1.3 Research Questions

Following are the questions to be taken into consideration while conducting this research.

- What are the risk management practice adopted in road construction project of Sindhupalchowk district, Province 3, Nepal during COVID-19?
- What are the risk factors along with its ranking and how could it be allocated at road construction project of Sindhupalchowk district, Province 3, Nepal during COVID-19?
- What is the impact of adopted risk management practice on success of road construction project?

1.4 Research Objectives

The overall objective of this research is to analyze the risk management practice along with its impact in road construction in Sindhupalchowk district with the perspective of global pandemic of coronavirus disease (COVID-19).

The specific objectives can be summarized below.

- To assess the practice of risk management adopted and check conformance to quality standards in selected road construction project in Sindhupalchowk district with COVID-19 perspective.
- To analyze risk factors and their ranking at workplace with the perspective of COVID-19 based on Failure Mode and Effect Analysis (FMEA).
- To analyze the impact of Risk Management Practice on success of road construction projects.

1.5 Significance of the Study

The study is significant for professional to understand the practices of risk management being adopted by Nepalese Contractors in the perspective of COVID-19 pandemic disease. It is significant to draw the attention of construction companies/professionals for better evaluation of risk factors and their management for ensuring project's success. The study is also significant for documenting the risk management practice to make it systematic by identifying significant factors and analyze the impact of risk management practice on success of road construction projects as well as other construction projects.

1.6 Scope and Limitations of the Study

Scope

This research explores the study of risk allocation and its impact in road construction project at Sindhupalchowk district, Province 3, Nepal. This research also analyzes the risk factors and their severity based on FMEA model.

Limitation

The limitations of this research are: -

- Only few basic test is performed to test the conformance to quality standards. Complex and higher order tests are beyond the scope of this study.
- This research is focused on risk management practice of Central Region (Sindhupalchowk district, Province 3) of Nepal only.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

The construction industry, with the development of science and technology has modified rapidly over the past condition within a decade. Construction firm are facing more risks and uncertainties as compared to past events. The expectation of owner has increased to more and more safe working environment and surety towards deliverables yet contractors are facing high risk event and their occurrence. Risk management has thus, become major highlight of the construction firms for any construction projects. Risk in construction industry is major focus topic in current time as time and cost overrun within the construction projects has become high impact risk factors.

2.1 Theoretical Review

2.1.1 Risk and Uncertainty

Risks are those uncertainties or conditions which when occurs, has both positive and negative impacts on deliverables of the project. Risk is generally expressed in terms of occurrence probability and its consequences, or impact on output of project. For any event to be taken as potential risk factor, it must have a probability of occurrence between 0 and 1, which explains to what extent, the risk event is likely to occur. Hence, the impact of risk factor can be stated when details related to possibility of occurrence and series of probable outcome with their likeliness to occur. (Smith et. al., 2014).

Risk, in mathematical terms can be defined as,

$$\text{Risk} = \text{Hazard} \times \text{Exposure}$$

Hazard is "the way in which an event can cause harm".

Exposure is "the limit to which the extent of harm can be influenced by hazard".

Uncertainty are those events to which the probability of occurrence is unknown, i.e. uncertainty are those events about which little is known related to extent of its occurrence with only possibility that it might occur. Uncertainty is said to exist when an event results in multiple possible outcome yet the probability of those outcome is unknown (Smith et al., 2014).

2.1.2 Sources of Risk

The risk can be categorized based on project specific risk and non-project specific risk. Risk related to both the categories needs to be considered during identification of risk factors within a project. Project team, during analysis of risk event needs to define the boundaries up to which the risk needs to be considered and break down the risk event into independent risk elements. This facilitates in easy understanding of the risk events and helps in better selection of risk response strategy.

The general checklist for source breakdown of risk includes commercial, financial, legal, political, environmental, communication, geographical, constructional, technological, operational, and management risks (Estate Management Manual, 2001).

2.1.3 Typical Risk in a Construction Project

Typical Risks in a Construction Project includes: -

- Accidents on site resulting in physical injury.
- Failure in completing the project as per design planned.
- Unable to accomplish project within estimated time duration.
- Failure to obtain the approval documents as per local authorities and legal requirements.
- Delay in project due to unforeseen site conditions.
- Price fluctuation and market uncertainty related to construction material and labor.
- Possibility of budget exceeding the upper boundary limit as per Client's expectation.
- Force majeure conditions.
- Failure to maintain project progress within the estimated cost.
- Loss to the contractor due to unaccounted events.
- Unable to take timely decision related to variation and uncertainties.
- Unable to achieve the required quality standards, Safety Health and Environment regulations etc. (Flanagan & Norman, 1993).

2.1.4 Risk Management Process

The process of risk management is broadly categorized into two distinct phases as risk assessment and risk control. The first phase, risk assessment includes identification of risk, analysis of risk and its ranking where-as risk control comprises of risk management plan, risk resolution, risk monitoring and taking preventive actions (Raz & Michael, 2001).

Risk management is formal systematic process of identification, assessment and response to the risk events throughout the life cycle of a project with goal to attain optimum control over project deliverables (Ahmed et al., 1999). Mishra and Malik (2017) suggests risk management process as an integrated approach with following activities: -

- Preliminary Activities
- Risk Identification
- Risk Assessment
- Risk Response Planning
- Risk Management Review

This risk management process along with flowchart is explained below.

Fig. 2.1 Flowchart of Risk Management Process (Mishra & Malik, 2017)

A. Risk Identification

The identification of risk is the major step in process of risk management. The aim of this process is to identify the potential risk events that has high impact on project goals. Identifying all the potential risk is an impossible task and thus the goal of risk identification should be to identify and assess the high value risk factors that has potential to cause huge impact such that, the control of such risk events enables project team to achieve the overall objective of project (Smith et al., 2014). Risk management is an ongoing process that adopts various approaches on different phases of project life cycle. Risk identification is the initial step in process of risk management and reports of previous similar project serves as primary basis for identification of the risk events. Risk can also be identified through literature review, brainstorming, risk register, questionnaire survey, key informant interview and past experience.

B. Risk Assessment

Assessment of risk provides detail description of the risk event, quantify the damage and prioritize them based on its severity. Assessment of risk event is based on cause and effect of the events that has potential to cause adverse impact on project which ultimately facilitates in decision making process (Estate Management Manual, 2001). The result of risk analysis is identification of all feasible options to manage risk and outcome associated with each decision adopted. Broadly risk can be analyzed through qualitative and quantitative approach where qualitative approach focuses on evaluation of impact and ranking of the risk and quantitative approach defines the severity of risk event in terms of high and low with its possibility of occurrence. Table 2.1 below shows various qualitative and quantitative methods of risk analysis.

Table 2.1 Various Risk Analysis Technique

Qualitative Analysis	Quantitative Analysis
a) Direct judgment	a) Probability analysis
b) Ranking options	b) Sensitivity analysis
c) Comparative analysis	c) Scenario analysis
d) Descriptive analysis	d) Simulation analysis

(Ward and Chapman, 1997)

C. Risk Response Practice

The final step in process of risk management is risk response that identifies the action to be taken to control the impact of risk event ensuring the success of the project (Mhetre et.al, 2016). PMBOK defines risk response planning as the set of activities that develop options and determine actions which reduce the impact of the threats and enhance the possibility of obtaining the desired output. Risk management responsibility is assigned to the party that can handle best the risk event and constant monitoring is done to measure the impact of risk on project success.

PMI (2017) suggests four risk response strategy in a projects, they are as follows:

- **Avoidance:** This completely eliminates risk by adopting different approach for the construction works.
- **Transfer:** It is the method of assigning the risk to other parties eg. to sub-contractor, to supplier, to insurer etc.)
- **Mitigation:** This is method of developing a plan to minimize the consequence or reduce probability of occurrence of risk event.
- **Acceptance:** This is method of dealing with the consequences when the risk event occurs.

2.2 Empirical Review on Risk Management

2.2.1 Global Practice of Risk Management

Petrovic (2017) in his paper “Risk Management in Construction Projects–A Knowledge Management Perspective from Swedish Contractors” found out that Swedish construction industry was fairly unknown about the process of risk management. Analogous methods were implemented though they were not as structured as per theoretical reports. The reason of inadequacy in implementation of risk management were insufficient project duration, capabilities and the work culture. He also concluded the absence of proper documentation of risk management plan.

As per the findings of research, common methods adopted for risk identification were past experience from similar projects, checklists and brainstorming. The most frequent risk response strategies adopted by contractors where risk avoidance then risk mitigation and finally accepting of the risk. Transfer of risks to the other party was quite common among developers. So, the implementation of risk management plan was more or less similar to theoretical concepts regarding risk identification and risk response but risk assessment differed from theoretical concept to a higher degree. The research concluded that the risk management practice adopted were only analogous to the theoretical concept yet systematic and structured process was not being followed by the by Swedish contractors.

Sharaf & Abaelwahab (2015) conducted study with title "Analysis of Risk factor for Highway construction project in Egypt". The research took into account the risk factors that frequently occurred on project life cycle and had significant impact on project completion. According to the study, the major risk factors in highway construction were delay in making decision and land acquisition which have risk factors values of more than 50% and likelihood over 70%. The fuzzy logic model was developed in order to evaluate project risk. The research found that based on the analysis, the overall risk in highway construction project in Egypt is considered at a medium level and needs to deploy the use of proper risk management.

El-Karim et.al. (2015) in their research paper “Identification and Assessment of Risk Factors affecting construction project” conducted study in Egypt where identification and assessment of the factors that affect time and cost of the project was evaluated. It was concluded that time and cost were two major factors of a construction project and thus, obtaining realistic budget and appropriate schedule was must for achieving project objectives successfully. The research was based on survey conducted to identify, assess and quantify the factors that affect budgetary and time constraints of a project. The research provided factors that had to be considered and their relative importance to estimate cost and schedule of the project for its successful completion.

Zou et.al (2007) in their article titled "Understanding the key risks in construction projects in China" conducted study to highlight the key risk events in construction project of China to develop appropriate risk response strategy to manage risk events. The risk events were classified based on its extent of influence on project deliverables in terms of quality, cost, time, safety health and environmental regulations. Twenty-five key risk factors were identified through postal questionnaire survey. It was concluded that government, consultant/designer and clients had to be responsible to manage the risk and contractor had to be responsible to maintain safe and efficient work environment at the construction sites.

2.2.2 Regional Practice of Risk Management

Parera et.al (2014) in their paper "Enhancing the effectiveness of risk management practices in Sri Lankan Road Construction Project" concluded that from the list of various identified risk factors during the project life cycle phases (conceptual, planning/design, construction and operational), one of the major risk was "design errors by consultant" that affected entire project life cycle (except conceptual phase). Based on its severity, it was second on list for the design and operation phase and fourth severe risk for the construction stage of project. "Delay in decision making by client" and "Error in estimation of duration and budget" were severe risk factor for conceptual phase as well as design phase. "Lack of funds for project" appeared prominent during design and construction phase of project and "Error committed during construction at site" was severe risk factor for the construction stage of project.

As per research findings, the construction stages in entire project life cycle was identified as most critical based on severity of risk factors. The risk factors identified during the construction stage ranked high based on its severity which was considered as the most important phase when exposed to externalities and human interaction. The research also stated that design phase was the second in the list in terms of vulnerability due to risk factors. So, additional care had to be taken during risk management strategy selection for both construction and design phases of project life cycle.

Sharma & Trivedi (2019) in their paper “Risk Analysis in Highway Construction Projects using Failure Mode & Effect Analysis” identified 48 risk factors by literature review and highway construction experts. As per their finding, insufficient availability of land appeared to be most important risk factor in highway construction projects. So, it was essential to acquire the required land prior to highway construction. Unforeseen climate condition was

second and uncertainty in land acquisition cost and schedule was third most important risk factors which affected the objectives of highway construction. In this research it was concluded that risk should be allocated to either clients or contractors or consultants related to project. It was clear that about 90% risks were allocated to contractors, so contractors were the most risks affected among project related parties. Risk response strategies were last but most important part of risk analysis. Four risk response strategies were found most suitable to response the risks which were avoidance, mitigation, transfer and acceptance of the risk event.

2.2.3 Risk Management Practice in Nepal

Mishra & Malik (2017) in their paper "Factor and impact of risk management practices on success of construction project of housing developers, Kathmandu Nepal" concluded that major risk factors in housing construction projects in Kathmandu valley were time overrun risk, project scope risk, financial risk, economic risk, organization risk, leadership risk and safety and health risk.

According to research finding top management were highly aware regarding risk management and was practicing it formally or informally with a mean score of 3.83. As per research finding, managements of Kathmandu valley were aware to some extent about risk management yet far behind in practical implementation of structured risk management approach. Major focus of managements was on risk related to time overrun and financial crisis.

The research also concluded that independent variables of risk management process (identification of risk, assessment of risk and risk response) had significant impact on eight out of ten project success criteria viz. well defined project scope, compliance to technical requirements, project within planned budget, compliance with the quality standard, project within schedule, controlled financial & economic risk, compliance to safety health and environmental requirements, overcome leadership risks. The independent variables had no impact on two out of ten success criteria viz. overcoming contractual risks and controlled organizational risk. Hence, it was concluded that risk management practice has significant impact in the success of project.

Mishra and Adhikari (2019) in their paper "Urban Road Construction Risk Management" concluded that contractor's top management awareness towards risk management was average with mean score of 3.44. They practiced risk management averagely either formally or informally by the urban road construction projects with mean score of 3.06. From the client's perspective their top management awareness about the process of risk management was high with mean score of 4.03. Similarly, practice of risk management either formal or informal was also found high with mean score of 4.0.

In their research, risk factors were investigated to measure the severity and allocation. Based on the contractor's perspective, land acquisition delay-shared with client, strike-avoided, payment problem-accepted by contractor, cash flow problem-transferred to client and corruption-avoided were identified as high risk factors with allocation. Based on client's perspective, most severe risks and their allocation were land acquisition delay-shared with contractor, strike-avoided, payment problem- shared with contractor, cash flow problem-accepted by client and corruption-avoided.

As per risk response strategy, according to research, transfer of risk to other parties of project was the most applied technique to prevent risk events by the contractor and depend on subjective judgment by the client. The most remedial strategy recommended by respondent was close supervision to minimize extra unplanned work and lastly change in the adopted method of construction works.

Shakya and Mishra (2019) in their research article “Risk Assessment in Construction of Gautam Buddha International Airport” concluded that no risk management approach was adopted in airport construction and thus all the issues impacting negatively were identified as the risk factors. Out of 96 risk factors categorized into 14 categories, risk factors significant from employer’s opinion was 33, consultant’s opinion was 41 and contractor’s opinion was 72 risk factors.

Unstructured risk management plan, poor assessment of site prior design, risk of hindrance in the airfield, dispute between consultant and contractor, communication difficulties among the working parties, inadequate control over cash flow, unsatisfactory status review, inability in taking corrective action timely for design and construction error, mismatch within structural and architectural drawing, inaccurate time estimates and scheduled and unsafe working conditions were some of the major risk factors based on its severity.

2.2.4 FEMA Model

Sharma & Trivedi (2019) in their paper “Risk Analysis in Highway Construction Projects using Failure Mode & Effect Analysis” adopted FMEA model for ranking the risk factors and determine the major risk factor that needs specialized attention. Questionnaire Survey was carried out to find Occurrence, Consequence and Detectability of each risk factor in terms of linguistic terms “Very High, High, Medium, Low & Very Low” and with the help of highway construction experts assigned crisp rating from 5 to 1 respectively. Risk factors were ranked based on Risk Priority Number (RPN) which was the product of Occurrence, Consequence and Detectability. FMEA table was designed in the last step of research which showed not only the rank of risk factor but also to whom risk should be allocated and which type of response should be given to each risk factor. In this research it was concluded that risk should be allocated to either clients or contractors or consultants related to project. It was clear from FMEA table that about 90% risks were allocated to contractors, so contractors were the most risks affected among project related parties.

2.2.5 Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19)

Mishra (2020) in his paper “Maintaining Productivity and Safety during COVID-19” has focused on the importance of safety in construction industry and its influence on productivity of construction project. Corona virus disease first appeared in Hubei, China in January 2020. Due to rapid spreading and lack of vaccine to treat the disease, WHO declared COVID-19 pandemic on 11th March, 2020. This pandemic has affected entire world economics and construction industry is not exceptional. This paper highlights the effects of corona virus disease in work site and suggests following measures of control as:

- a) Elimination/ Substitution: Working remotely, Virtual meetings, online trainings.
- b) Engineering Control: Isolation, Installation of physical Barriers.
- c) Administrative Control: Awareness/ Training, Posture/Sign/Symbol/Signage.
- d) PPEs: Safety Gloves/Mask/Googles/Face Shield, Safety Shoes/boots, Apron.

The study concludes that ensuring workplace safe from corona virus disease is a challenge and thus proper preparatory actions must be undertaken before resuming works.

CHAPTER 3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Flow Process

For the purpose of research plan or to obtain the findings from the systematic structured way of collecting the primary data and secondary data from the online / offline sources with the methodological framework has been described here.

Fig. 3.1 Methodological Framework

3.2 Study Area

The study is conducted at various areas of Sindhupalchowk district, Province 3, Nepal. Many studies have been conducted at central valley on nation however such research have been lacking in other areas. Geology of Sindhupalchowk is characterized by loose soil, frequent large scale landslides like Jure Landslide. With a total death count of 156, Jure landslide was one of the devastating landslides in history of Nepal. The reach of landslide was 1.26 km height and 0.81 km width at the bottom. Along with other destruction of infrastructures, it created a 55 m-high dam in the Sunkoshi River with the potential to cause huge flood and destruction. For construction of roads, hilly region with such land characteristics induces huge amount of risk which is the main region for selecting Sindhupalchowk district as the study area.

Fig. 3.2 Landslide Susceptibility of Sindhupalchowk District

The selected road projects are: -

- “Construction of Black Top of Sukute-Chapagaun-Meldanda-Thokarpa-Bhanjyang Road, Sindhupalchowk (Contract No: - DROCHT/3371234/073/74-191)”. The Employer is Ministry of Physical Infrastructure Development, Provincial Road Division Office, Khurkot and the Contractor is Gauriparvati Nirman Sewa Pvt. Ltd. The total length of roadway construction is 10.5 KM with estimated cost of 415.24 million rupees.

- “Construction of Black Top of Barabise-Thotanaari-Ratamate-Chulthidamar-Ghunde-Om Park Road, Sindhupalchowk (Contract No: - DROCHT/3371234/073/074-192)”. The Employer is Ministry of Physical Infrastructure Development, Provincial Road Division Office, Khurkot and the contractor is Lumbini/ Bandan Bhagwati/ Dragon JV. Total length of roadway to be construction is 8 KM with an estimated cost of 475.35 million rupees.
- “Construction of Black Top Work of Filmcity Access Road, Dolakha (Contract No: - DROCHT/3371234/073/074-123)”. The Employer is Ministry of Physical Infrastructure Development, Provincial Road Division Office, Khurkot and the Contractor is M/s Lama Construction and Suppliers Pvt. Ltd. The total length of roadway construction is 6 KM with estimated cost of 113.97 million rupees.
- “Widening and Upgrading of Khagdal-Kukure-Kalleri-Sigarche Road, Sindhupalchowk (Contract No: - DROCHT/3371234/073/74-194)”. The Employer is Ministry of Physical Infrastructure Development, Provincial Road Division Office, Khurkot and the Contractor is Rautaha/Himali Devdhunga/Om Buddha J.V. The total length of roadway construction is 4.5 KM with estimated cost of 153.18 million rupees.

Fig. 3.3 Road Network Map of Sindhupalchowk District

3.3 Study Population

For this research, study population are technical staffs of Ministry of Physical Infrastructure Development, Provincial Road Division Office, Khurkot, consulting firms, engineers, technical staffs of contractor working in road construction projects at Sindhupalchowk district.

3.4 Sampling Method

This research is based on extensive and complex structured with questionnaire beyond the understanding capabilities of general public. Thus, purposive sampling method is used for selecting sample for study where the researcher relies on its own judgment for choosing the respondents for the research study. Such facilitates researcher to obtain accurate response to the questionnaire ultimately enhancing the reliability of the research findings.

3.5 Sample Size

Sample is part of population chosen for the purpose of study. Sample of smaller size may not accurately portray the actual site condition whereas very large sample size though gives better result may be way beyond time and budget constraints. Thus sample size of 30 is chosen based on budget constraints and time available to conduct the research.

3.6 Data Collection

Data is collected from primary and secondary source which are both qualitative and quantitative to analyze the risk management practice adopted at Sindhupalchowk district, Province 3, Nepal.

3.6.1 Primary Data

The primary data for the study was obtained by:

- a) Key Informant Interview: To find out the managerial aspects, planning aspects, construction safety plan adopted, project in-charge and project manager will be interviewed.
- b) Questionnaire Survey: A simple set of questions will be prepared regarding hazard and risk associated with the construction project.
- c) Field Observation: Field visit will be done for visual assessment of the construction procedure.
- d) Lab Test: In order to access the quality of road construction, Laboratory tests for each Sub-base, Base and Bitumen Course will be conducted. The testing procedure is explained below:

1. Sieve Analysis of Aggregates

This test is used for determining the gradation of aggregates.

Apparatus Required: Balance, Sieve, Weighing Machine

Testing Procedure:

The weight of sample taken shall according to the weight given in Table-II (IS 2386 – Part I – 1963). Preparation of sample is done from larger sample through sample divider. Before weighing and sieving, sample is brought to air dry condition. Sieves are cleaned and dried prior to use and arranged in descending order. The air dried sample is weighed and then sieved for a period of at least two minutes. The shaking is done in fluctuating motion, right to left, forward & backward, clockwise & anti-clockwise to ensure frequent movement of material over the sieve. Brushing on the underside of the sieve with a soft brush is permitted to clear the openings of a sieve. Application of pressure to force particles through the mesh is strictly prohibited. After sieving is complete, material retained on each sieve is weighted to determine the gradation index of aggregates (IS 2386 – Part I – 1963).

2. Los Angles Abrasion Test

This test on sub-base and base material measures the toughness of aggregate and its resistance to abrasion, degradation, crushing and disintegration. The test procedure for abrasion value of aggregates involved following steps as per IS 2386-4 (1963).

The 10 kg aggregate sample is taken and placed on the Los Angles apparatus and the cover is fixed. Then the machine is rotated at a speed of 30 to 33 rpm. The machine is balanced to ensure uniform speed.

The machine is operated for required revolution number and then aggregate is discharged into a tray. The dust particles formed due to abrasion is sieved on IS sieve 1.70 mm and material retained on 1.70 mm sieve is weighed.

$$\text{Observed Abrasion Value} = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_1} * 100$$

Where, W_1 is the weight of original sample of aggregate

W_2 is the weight of retained sample of aggregate

3. Aggregate Impact Value Test

Aggregates are subjected to impact during vehicular movement on the surface of wearing course. Such impact results in breakdown of aggregates into smaller pieces. Thus aggregates must have sufficient strength to withstand the impact caused due to vehicular flow. This strength is measured in terms of aggregate impact value as resistance to sudden impact. The test procedure for aggregate impact value test is stated below as per IS 2386-4 (1963).

Test Procedure:

Aggregate impact value is generally calculated for surface dressing chips of size 12.5 mm to 10 mm. Sample must be air dried by heating at about 110°C for tentative 4 hours and then cooled to room temperature. The sample is sieved through IS sieves 12.5 mm and 10 mm. The material retained on 12.5 mm sieve is taken as the test sample.

A measuring cylinder is taken and test sample is filled up to 1/3rd height. The material is compacted by 25 blows of the tamping rod from rounded end. In the similar manner, two more layers is added and then surplus aggregates are stroked off. The aggregate is weighed to obtain W_1 in grams.

Impact testing machine is taken and brought to rest such that hammer guide columns are vertical. To compact the test sample, 25 strokes of tamping rod are used, whole sample taken at a time. Again the hammer is brought at a height of 380 mm above the top of sample and allowed to fall freely. A total of 15 blows are acted on the sample at an interval of one second between successive blows.

Now, the crushed material is taken and sieved through 2.36 mm IS sieve for about one minute. The fraction of aggregate passing through 2.36 mm sieve is weighted to obtain W_2 reading in grams. Then impact value of aggregate is obtained as: -

$$\text{Aggregate Impact Value} = \frac{W_2}{W_1} * 100$$

Where, W_1 is total sample weight taken

W_2 is weight of material passing through 2.36 mm sieve

3.6.2 Secondary Data

The secondary data were collected through detailed engineering project design report, published journals, published articles, different websites and existing legal provisions from concerned regulatory departments.

3.7 Data Analysis

A. To assess the practice of risk management adopted

Risk management practice adopted by Nepalese contractor is analyzed through set of statements related to risk management practice for which response are collected based on 1 to 5 Likert scale rating. Qualitative analysis of the response of questionnaire survey is done by MS-Excel. Following steps is conducted.

- Coding and defining the scale factors for linguistic meaning.
- Collecting and recording the data.

- Entering data on an Excel sheet
- Calculating the Mean score for each question based on rating provided by respondents between 1 and 5 where 1 means strong disagreement and 5 means strong agreement on Likert Scale.

$$\text{Mean Score} = \frac{\sum (f \times s)}{N}$$

Where, f is the frequency of responses to individual rating

S is the score given by respondent to the questions

N is the total number of response (Chan & Kumaraswamy, 1997)

❖ Reliability Test:

Cronbach's alpha is used to measure the reliability and validity of the response obtained during the questionnaire survey. It is the function of variance of the total score, variance of the item pair and number of question for a given set of data. The value of alpha lies between 0 and 1 where higher value of alpha closer to 1 is more desirable. Value of alpha less than 0.6 shows unreliability of data obtained, value of alpha between 0.7 to 0.8 means acceptable response, value of alpha between 0.8 and 0.9 means good response and value of alpha above 0.9 shows excellence in reliability of data obtained through questionnaire. Formula to calculate Cronbach's alpha is shown below.

$$\alpha = \frac{K}{K-1} \left(1 - \frac{\sum V_i}{V_t} \right)$$

Where,

K = No. of Questions

V_i = Variance of score on each question

V_t = Total Variance of overall scores on entire set of question

❖ Setting up Hypothesis for Compliance with Quality Standard

Type of Test Statistics: Chi-Square Test

Purpose of Test: To check goodness of fit i.e. to test how well a sample of data matches the well-established quality standards for road construction works.

Null Hypothesis H₀: All sites achieve the required quality standards i.e. there is no significance difference between quality parameters at site condition and quality standards.

Alternate Hypothesis H₁: All site does not achieve the required quality standards.

B. To analyze risk factors and their severity at workplace based on Failure Mode and Effect Analysis (FMEA).

The analysis of data is done to rank the risk factors based on its severity in road construction project. As per FMEA model following steps will be carried out.

Step 1: Identification of Risk Factors

Risk Factors is identified through literature review and discussion with highway construction experts. Questionnaire survey is performed to obtain Crisp Rating for Risk Occurrence (RO), Risk Consequence (RC) and Risk Detectability (RD). Crisp rating will be in the scale of 1 to 5 where “1 means Very Low probability, 2 means Low probability, 3 means Medium probability, 4 means High probability and 5 means Very High probability”.

Step 2: Index calculation based on Relative Importance Index (RII) Method

As per RII concept ROI, RCI & RDI of each risk factor is calculated using following formulas.

$$\text{Risk Occurrence Index (ROI)} = \frac{\sum W}{A * N}$$

$$\text{Risk Consequence Index (RCI)} = \frac{\sum W}{A * N}$$

$$\text{Risk Detectability Index (RDI)} = \frac{\sum W}{A * N}$$

Where, $\sum W$ = Sum of responses i.e. sum of crisp rating of factor given by respondents,

A = Maximum value of crisp rating which is 5

N = No. of respondents

Step 3: RPN Calculation

Risk Priority Number (RPN) is multiplication of Risk Occurrence, Risk Consequence and Risk Detectability. In this research ROI, RCI and RDI are calculated using relative importance index formula. Values of ROI, RCI and RDI are less than one, so the multiplication of ROI, RCI and RDI will be in decimal. To understand and compare the RPN of different-different risk events, resulted multiplication of ROI, RCI, RDI is multiplied by 100. Thus proposed formula to calculate RPN is-

$$\text{RPN} = \text{ROI} \times \text{RCI} \times \text{RDI} \times 100$$

Step 4: Ranking of Risk Factors

After calculating RPN of each risk factor using above formula, to determine the severity of Risk Factors, its ranking is done on the basis of Risk Priority Number (RPN) of risk factors. Higher the RPN, Higher the Risk. Thus Ranking of Risk Factors will be done as per decreasing order of RPN in such a way that the rank of maximum RPN is one with highest severity. (Sharma & Trivedi, 2019).

C. To analyze the impact of Risk Management Practice on success road construction projects.

Regression model of hypothesis testing is adopted to find the impact of risk management practice on success of road construction project in context of Nepal. Independent variable for hypothesis testing is taken as three process of risk management as Risk Identification, Risk Assessment and Risk Response. Dependent variables for hypothesis are the project success criteria based on top ten risk factors obtained through FMEA model of risk ranking. Finally, regression hypothesis testing is done to analyze the impact of risk management practice on success of construction project.

Fig. 3.4 Research Model for Hypothesis Testing

Setting the Hypothesis

Null Hypothesis: H_0A : There is no impact of Risk Identification on Project Success.

Alternate Hypothesis: H_1A : There is impact of Risk Identification on Project Success.

H_{1A1} : There is impact of Risk Identification on 1st Success Criteria.

H_{1A2} : There is impact of Risk Identification on 2nd Success Criteria.

.....

H_{1A10} : There is impact of Risk Identification on 10th Success Criteria.

Similarly

Null Hypothesis: H_0B : There is no impact of Risk Assessment on Project Success.

Alternate Hypothesis: H_1B : There is impact of Risk Assessment on Project Success.

H_{1B1} : There is impact of Risk Assessment on 1st Success Criteria.

H_{1B2} : There is impact of Risk Assessment on 2nd Success Criteria.

.....

H_{1B10} : There is impact of Risk Assessment on 10th Success Criteria.

Finally,

Null Hypothesis: H_0C : There is no impact of Risk Response on Project Success.

Alternate Hypothesis: H_1C : There is impact of Risk Response on Project Success.

H_{1C1} : There is impact of Risk Response on 1st Success Criteria.

H_{1C2} : There is impact of Risk Response on 2nd Success Criteria.

.....

H_{1C10} : There is impact of Risk Response on 10th Success Criteria.

3.8 Expected Result

The expected result of this research will be: -

- Risk Management Practice that is being adopted by Nepalese Contractors at Sindhupalchowk district, Province 1, Nepal in perspective of COVID-19.
- Lab test results to confer the quality of materials and workmanship to achieve the desired quality as per standard.
- Various risk factors and their severity in the work place based on FMEA model along with COVID-19 perspective.
- The impact of risk management parameters on success of a project.

3.9 Summary of Methodology

The summary of methodology is compiled in the table below.

Table 3.1 Research Matrix

S. N	Objectives	Data Required	Collection tool	Data Analysis
1	To access the practice of risk management adopted and check conformance to quality standards in selected road construction project in Sindhupalchowk district	Awareness about the potential hazards Formal or informal techniques being followed to predict all hazards associated with the project Sample for lab testing	Questionnaire survey with key personnel. Key Informant Interview Laboratory testing of the sample obtained	Descriptive Statistical Analysis Mathematical analysis and Hypothesis Testing of data obtained from lab testing
2	To analyze risk factors and their ranking at workplace with the perspective of COVID-19 based on Failure Mode and Effect Analysis (FMEA).	Data related to Project scope, budget, design specification, Quality, leadership, organizational, contractual documents, financial and economic, safety health and environment	Questionnaire survey with key personnel. Key Informant Interview Secondary data through research papers, literature review, journals and publications.	Failure Mode and Effect Analysis (FMEA) Risk Ranking based on Risk Priority Number
3	To analyze the impact of Risk Management Practice on success of road construction projects	Various potential risk of project and their impacts.	Questionnaire survey with key personnel. Key Informant Interview Secondary data through research papers, literature review, journals & publications.	Hypothesis Testing

CHAPTER 4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research was conducted through questionnaire survey to analyze the practice of risk management on the road construction project at Sindhupalchowk District, Province 3, Nepal. The result obtained from this research concludes that there exist impacts between the risk management practice with success of project. This research also evaluates significant risk factors based on their probability of occurrence, consequence and detectability in case of road construction project. MS Excel was used to analyze the collected data and findings are presented below.

4.1 Risk Management Practice

Risk management practice of road construction project at Sindhupalchowk District, Province 3, Nepal has been obtained from the contractor's and client's perspective.

4.1.1 Risk Management Practice, Contractor's Perspective

The practice of risk management adopted by contractor has been analyzed through questionnaire survey given in Appendix I. A total of 30 responses were collected from technical persons directly or indirectly related with the study area at Sindhupalchowk District. Risk management practice of road construction projects has been obtained from the statistics of management awareness regarding risk management, statistics of management formally/informally practicing risk management, statistics of management practicing the risk management formally and statistics of management analyzing various risk management techniques. The response received is shown in Appendix II.

A. Management Awareness Regarding Risk Management Practice, Contractor's Perspective

As per the 30 responses received during the research, it was observed that management awareness regarding the risk management as average with the mean score of 3.30 on Likert scale.

Table 4.1 Management Awareness Regarding Risk Management, Contractor's Perspective

Rate	Frequency	Percentage	Mean Score	S.D.
1(Least Aware)	0	0	3.30	0.53
2	1	3.33		
3	19	63.34		
4	10	33.33		
5(Most Aware)	0	0		
Total	30	100		

From the table 4.1, no response was obtained on scale 1 which means every management was little aware about risk management. Majority of respondents i.e. 63.34% of total rated 3 i.e. these managements were averagely aware regarding the risk management. 33.33% of total rated 4 i.e. these managements were often aware regarding the risk management. Lowest 3.33% out of total rated 2 which means these managements were rarely aware regarding the risk management.

During key informant interview, management awareness regarding risk related to COVID – 19 pandemics was found high. Management were completely aware about social distancing and quarantining measures. The use of face mask and hand sanitizer, frequent hand washing, covering cough and sneeze, adequate ventilation of indoor spaces was well known to the contractor’s management.

From the Mishra & Malik (2017), management awareness regarding risk management from housing developers gives the means score of 4.03. From Mishra & Adhikari (2019), management awareness regarding risk management from urban road construction gives mean score of 3.44. However, management awareness at Sindhupalchowk district is slightly less comparatively with mean score of 3.30.

B. Management Practicing Risk Management Formally or Informally, Contractor’s Perspective

As per the 30 responses received during the research, it was observed that managements are averagely practicing the risk management with the mean score of 3.03 on Likert scale.

Table 4.2 Management Practicing Risk Management Formally or Informally, Contractor’s Perspective

Rate	Frequency	Percentage	Mean Score	S.D.
1(Least Practice)	0	0	3.03	0.48
2	3	10		
3	23	76.67		
4	4	13.33		
5(Most Practice)	0	0		
Total	30	100		

From the table 4.2, no response was obtained on scale 1 meaning each of the management was practicing risk management to some extent. Most of the respondents i.e. 76.67% of total rated 3 i.e. these managements were averagely practicing risk management. 13.33% of total rated 4 i.e. these managements were often practicing risk management. Lowest 10% out of total rated 2 i.e. these managements were rarely practicing risk management formally or informally.

During key informant interview, management practicing risk management in response to COVID – 19 pandemics was found satisfactory. The use of mask was found implemented satisfactorily at the construction sites however no hand sanitizer or proper hand washing facilities were available at sites.

From the Mishra & Malik (2017), management practicing risk management from housing developers gives the means score of 3.86. From Mishra & Adhikari (2019), management practicing risk management from urban road construction gives mean score of 3.06. However, management practicing risk management at Sindhupalchowk district is slightly less comparatively with mean score of 3.03.

C. Management Practicing Risk Management Formally, Contractor’s Perspective

As per the 30 responses received during the research, it was observed that managements are averagely practicing the risk management formally with the mean score of 2.83 on Likert scale.

Table 4.3 Management Practicing Risk Management Formally, Contractor’s Perspective

Rate	Frequency	Percentage	Mean Score	S.D.
1(Least Practice)	0	0	2.83	0.58
2	8	26.67		
3	19	63.33		
4	3	10		
5(Most Practice)	0	0		
Total	30	100		

From the table 4.3, no response was obtained on scale 1 meaning each of management was practicing risk management formally to some extent. Most of the respondents i.e. 63.33% of total rated 3 i.e. these managements were averagely practicing risk management formally. 26.67% of total rated 2 i.e. these managements were rarely practicing risk management. Lowest 10% out of total rated 4 i.e. these managements were often practicing risk management formally.

During key informant interview, management practicing risk management formally in response to COVID – 19 pandemics was found below satisfactory level. Proper use of face mask was not seen among most of the site personnel. Adequate quarantine facility, hand sanitizer, well sanitized facilities were lacking at the site. Social distancing was major challenge as per response of the interviewee.

From the Mishra & Malik (2017), management practicing risk management from housing developers gives the means score of 3.36. From Mishra & Adhikari (2019), management practicing risk management from urban road construction gives mean score of 3.06. However, managements practicing risk management formally at Sindhupalchowk district is much less comparatively with mean score of 2.83.

D. Management Analyzing Various Risk Management Techniques, Contractor’s Perspective

As per the 30 responses received during the research, it was observed that managements are averagely analyzing risk management technique with the mean score of 3.07 on Likert scale.

Table 4.4 Management Analyzing Various Risk Management Techniques, Contractor’s Perspective

Rate	Frequency	Percentage	Mean Score	S.D.
1(Least Analyzed)	0	0	3.07	0.68
2	6	20		
3	16	53.33		
4	8	26.67		
5(Most Analyzed)	0	0		
Total	30	100		

From the table 4.4, no response was obtained on scale 1 meaning each of management was analyzing risk management technique to some extent. Most of the respondents i.e. 53.33% of total rated 3 i.e. these managements were averagely analyzing risk management technique. 26.67% of total rated 4 i.e. these managements were often analyzing risk management technique. Lowest 20% out of total rated 2 i.e. these managements were rarely analyzing risk management technique.

In response to COVID – 19 pandemics, as per key informant interview, management were not found to have taking necessary precautionary measures to control the risk of corona virus disease. COVID pandemic was taken very lightly, regular disinfection of the site facilities was not adopted, provision of quarantining the facility upon infection was not performed at most of the sites.

From Mishra & Adhikari (2019), management analyzing risk management technique from urban road construction gives mean score of 1.96. However, managements analyzing risk management technique at Sindhupalchowk district is much more comparatively with mean score of 3.07.

E. Risk Identification Techniques Used, Contractor’s Perspective

Out of 30 response received from survey, following chart shows frequency of various risk identification techniques used by management for road construction in Sindhupalchowk District.

As per the response received, mostly adopted risk identification technique in Sindhupalchowk district are Expert Opinion and Monitoring and Evaluation report of similar past projects. 63.33% of the respondent used Monitoring and Evaluation report of similar past projects whereas 60% of the respondents used Expert Opinion as well to identify various risk factors. 10% and 13.33% respondent adopts contract document and brainstorming respectively as source of risk identification technique. The least used technique for risk identification was observed to be risk register where only one respondent claimed to use risk register to identify various risk factors. The comparative analysis can be seen through bar chart shown below.

Fig. 4.1 Comparative use of Risk Identification Techniques, Contractor's Perspective

F. Risk Analysis Techniques Used, Contractor's Perspective

Out of 30 response received from survey, following chart shows frequency of various risk analysis techniques used by management for road construction in Sindhupalchowk District.

Fig. 4.2 Comparative use of Risk Analysis Techniques, Contractor's Perspective

From figure 4.2, mostly adopted risk analysis technique in Sindhupalchowk district is Direct Judgment. 76.67% of the respondent used Direct Judgment to analyze various risk parameters. Secondly used analysis technique were comparative and descriptive analysis used by 43.33% and 23.33% respondents respectively. The least used techniques for risk analysis were observed to be probability analysis and ranking options by two and four respondents only. No respondent claimed to have used sensitivity, scenario and simulation analysis for risk analysis which shows complexity in the use of above technique. Thus training program is recommended for these techniques of risk analysis at Sindhupalchowk district. The comparative analysis can be seen through bar chart shown above.

G. Risk Response Strategy Used, Contractor’s Perspective

Out of 30 response received from survey, following chart shows frequency of various risk response strategy used by management for road construction in Sindhupalchowk District.

Fig. 4.3 Comparative use of Risk Response Strategy, Contractor’s Perspective

From figure 4.3, mostly adopted risk response strategy in Sindhupalchowk district was monitoring the risk and preparing contingency plan. 66.67% of the respondent adopted this technique as risk response strategy. Similarly, with more or less equal response, mitigating, avoiding and transferring risks were widely used by 23.33%, 20% and 16.67% respectively. The least used strategy for risk response was observed to be accepting the risk where only 6.67% respondent claimed to accept the risk depending upon the severity of risk factor. The comparative analysis can be seen through bar chart shown above.

Cronbach's alpha was calculated to test the reliability of response obtained regarding risk management practice of Sindhupalchowk district based on contractor's perspective. The value of Cronbach's alpha is shown below.

Table 4.5 Reliability Statistics for Risk Management Practice, Contractor's Perspective

No. of Questions (K)	No. of Respondents (N)	Value of Cronbach's Alpha
4	30	0.842

Here, value of Cronbach's alpha for response related to risk management practice based on contractor's perspective lies above 0.8. Hence, the internal consistency of data is good.

4.1.2 Risk Management Practice, Client's Perspective

The practice of risk management adopted by client has been analyzed through questionnaire survey given in Appendix I. A total of 15 responses were collected from technical persons directly or indirectly related with the study area at Sindhupalchowk District. Risk management practice of road construction projects has been obtained from the statistics of management awareness regarding risk management, statistics of management practicing risk management formally/informally, statistics of management practicing the risk management formally and statistics of management analyzing various risk management techniques. The response received based on client's perspective is shown in Appendix II.

A. Management Awareness Regarding Risk Management Practice, Client's Perspective

As per the 15 responses received during the research, it was observed that managements are often aware regarding the risk management with the mean score of 3.93 on Likert scale.

Table 4.6 Management Awareness Regarding Risk Management, Client's Perspective

Rate	Frequency	Percentage	Mean Score	S.D.
1(Least Aware)	0	0	3.93	0.68
2	0	0		
3	4	26.67		
4	8	53.33		
5(Most Aware)	3	20		
Total	15	100		

From the table 4.6, no response was obtained on scale 1 and 2 meaning each management was little aware regarding risk management. Most of the respondents i.e. 53.33% of total rated 4 i.e. these managements were often aware regarding the risk management. 26.67% of total rated 3 i.e. these managements are averagely aware regarding the risk management. Lowest 20% out of total rated 5 i.e. these managements were highly aware regarding the risk management.

During key informant interview, management awareness regarding risk related to COVID – 19 pandemics was found high. Management were completely aware about social distancing and quarantining measures. The use of face mask and hand sanitizer, frequent hand washing, covering cough and sneeze, adequate ventilation of indoor spaces was well known to the client’s management.

From the Mishra & Malik (2017), management awareness regarding risk management from housing developers gives the means score of 4.03. From Mishra & Adhikari (2019), management awareness regarding risk management from urban road construction gives mean score of 4.08. However, management awareness at Sindhupalchowk district based on client’s perspective is slightly less comparatively with mean score of 3.93.

B. Management Practicing Risk Management Formally or Informally, Client’s Perspective

As per the 15 responses received during the research, it was observed that managements are averagely practicing the risk management with the mean score of 3.33 on Likert scale.

Table 4.7 Management Practicing Risk Management Formally or Informally, Client’s Perspective

Rate	Frequency	Percentage	Mean Score	S.D.
1(Least Practice)	0	0	3.33	0.47
2	0	0		
3	10	66.67		
4	5	33.33		
5(Most Practice)	0	0		
Total	15	100		

From the table 4.7, no response was obtained on scale 1 and 2 meaning each management was practicing risk management to some extent. Most of the respondents i.e. 66.67% of total rated 3 i.e. these managements were averagely practicing risk management. 33.33% of total rated 4 i.e. these managements were often practicing risk management.

During key informant interview, management practicing risk management in response to COVID – 19 pandemics was found satisfactory. The use of mask was found implemented well at their office as well as construction sites. Adequate use of hand sanitizer or proper hand washing facilities were available as per client’s management. Sufficient care was done to control the risk of spread of corona virus disease, however social distancing was still a challenge to satisfactorily achieve the required standard.

From the Mishra & Malik (2017), management practicing risk management from housing developers gives the means score of 3.83. From Mishra & Adhikari (2019), management practicing risk management from urban road construction gives mean score of 4.00. However, management practicing risk management at Sindhupalchowk district based on client’s perspective is slightly less comparatively with mean score of 3.33.

C. Management Practicing Risk Management Formally, Client's Perspective

As per the 15 responses received during the research, it was observed that managements are averagely practicing the risk management formally with the mean score of 3.13 on Likert scale.

Table 4.8 Management Practicing Risk Management Formally, Client's Perspective

Rate	Frequency	Percentage	Mean Score	S.D.
1(Least Practice)	0	0	3.13	0.34
2	0	0		
3	13	86.67		
4	2	13.33		
5(Most Practice)	0	0		
Total	15	100		

From the table 4.8, no response was obtained on scale 1 and 2 meaning each management was practicing risk management formally to some extent. Most of the respondents i.e. 86.67% of total rated 3 i.e. these managements were averagely practicing risk management formally. Remaining 13.33% out of total rated 4 i.e. these managements were often practicing risk management formally.

During key informant interview, management practicing risk management formally in response to COVID – 19 pandemics was found good. Proper use of face mask covering complete mouth and nose was observed. Hand sanitizer, well sanitized facilities were available at their working environment. Social distancing, though implemented to a certain level, was still a challenge as per response of the interviewee.

From the Mishra & Malik (2017), management practicing risk management from housing developers gives the means score of 3.36. From Mishra & Adhikari (2019), management practicing risk management from urban road construction gives mean score of 3.66. However, managements practicing risk management formally at Sindhupalchowk district based on client's perspective is slightly less comparatively with mean score of 3.13.

D. Management Analyzing Various Risk Management Techniques, Client's Perspective

As per the 15 responses received during the research, it was observed that managements are averagely analyzing risk management technique with the mean score of 3.40 on Likert scale.

Table 4.9 Management Analyzing Various Risk Management Techniques, Client's Perspective

Rate	Frequency	Percentage	Mean Score	S.D.
1(Least Analyzed)	0	0	3.40	0.49
2	0	0		
3	9	60		
4	6	40		
5(Most Analyzed)	0	0		
Total	30	100		

From the table 4.9, no response was obtained on scale 1 and 2 meaning each management was analyzing risk management technique to some extent. Most of the respondents i.e. 60% of total rated 3 i.e. these managements were averagely analyzing risk management technique. 40% of total rated 4 i.e. these managements were often analyzing risk management technique.

In response to COVID – 19 pandemics, as per key informant interview, management were found to have taking necessary precautionary measures to control the risk of corona virus disease. COVID pandemic was taken seriously. Regular disinfection of the site facilities, sufficient quarantine period for infected employee, provision of quarantining the facility upon infection was performed by client’s management.

From Mishra & Adhikari (2019), management analyzing risk management technique from urban road construction gives mean score of 2.88. However, managements analyzing risk management technique at Sindhupalchowk district based on client’s perspective is much more comparatively with mean score of 3.40.

E. Risk Identification Techniques Used, Client’s Perspective

Out of 15 response received from survey, following chart shows frequency of various risk identification techniques used by management for road construction in Sindhupalchowk District.

Fig. 4.4 Comparative use of Risk Identification Techniques, Client’s Perspective

From figure 4.4, mostly adopted risk identification technique by client’s management in Sindhupalchowk district is Monitoring and Evaluation report of similar past projects. 93.33% of the respondent used Monitoring and Evaluation report of similar past projects. 26.67%, 33.33% and 40% respondent adopts brainstorming, contract document and expert

opinion respectively as source of risk identification technique. The least used technique for risk identification was observed to be risk register where none respondent claimed to use risk register to identify various risk factors. The comparative analysis can be seen through bar chart shown above.

F. Risk Analysis Techniques Used, Client’s Perspective

Out of 15 response received from survey, following chart shows frequency of various risk analysis techniques used by management for road construction in Sindhupalchowk District.

Fig. 4.5 Comparative use of Risk Analysis Techniques, Client’s Perspective

From figure 4.5, mostly adopted risk analysis technique in Sindhupalchowk district is Direct Judgment. 100% of the respondent used Direct Judgment to analyze various risk parameters. Secondly used analysis technique were ranking options and comparative analysis used by 40% and 26.67% respondents respectively. The least used techniques for risk analysis were observed to be probability analysis by 20% respondents only. No respondent claimed to have used descriptive analysis, sensitivity, scenario and simulation analysis for risk analysis which shows complexity in use of above technique and thus training program is recommended for these techniques of risk analysis.

G. Risk Response Strategy Used, Client’s Perspective

Out of 15 response received from survey, following chart shows frequency of various risk response strategy used by management for road construction in Sindhupalchowk District.

Fig. 4.6 Comparative use of Risk Response Strategy, Client's Perspective

From figure 4.6, mostly adopted risk response strategy by client's management in Sindhupalchowk district was transferring the risk to contractor. 100% of the client respondents adopted risk transfer as risk response strategy. Similarly, with more or less equal response, avoiding and monitoring risk and preparing contingency plan were used by 26.67% and 33.33% respectively. None of the client respondent adopted accepting and mitigating the risk as a risk response strategy.

Cronbach's alpha was calculated to test the reliability of response obtained regarding risk management practice of Sindhupalchowk district based on client's perspective. The value of Cronbach's alpha is shown below.

Table 4.10 Reliability Statistics for Risk Management Practice, Client's Perspective

No. of Questions (K)	No. of Respondents (N)	Value of Cronbach's Alpha
4	15	0.875

Here, value of Cronbach's alpha for response related to risk management practice based on client's perspective lies above 0.8. Hence, the internal consistency of data is good.

4.2 Conformance to Quality Standards

The quality of materials to be used for construction of roads as well as the specification to be achieved is specified in Standard Specification for Road and Bridge Works, 2073 prepared by Department of Roads, Planning and Design Branch, Central Road Laboratory. Following lab tests were conducted to check the conformance of construction materials to required quality standards.

4.2.1 Gradation of Base Material

Aggregate for base course was collected from site and sieve analysis was performed to find the gradation of material use for base course. Table 4.11 below shows detail weights of material retained in various sieve sizes along with percentage passing.

Table 4.11 Sieve Analysis Report of Base Material

Sieve Size Mm	Weight Retained gm	Weight Passing gm	% Passing	Upper and Lower Limit
53	0	13409	100	100
45	480	12929	96.42	95-100
22.40	3520	9409	70.17	60-80
11.20	2844	6565	48.96	40-60
4.75	2218	4347	32.42	25-40
2.36	682	3665	27.33	15-30
0.60	1006	2659	19.83	8-22
0.075	1102	1557	11.61	0-5
Pan	1557			
Total Weight	13409			

The particle size distribution curve of sample obtained from site condition shows excess of fines material about 11.61% which is higher than the standard range of (0-5) % as per Standard Specification for Road and Bridge Works 2073. Particles of other size range lies within the standard limit. The particle size distribution curve is shown in the graph below.

Fig. 4.7 Particle Size Distribution Curve

4.2.2 Gradation of Premix Chips

Aggregate chips to be used for premix carpet should be uniformly dense graded with particles size 13mm down. Sample was collected from site conditions and sieve analysis was performed to determine the gradation of premix chips. Table 4.12 shows complete gradation details of premix chips from Sukute site.

Table 4.12 Gradation of Aggregate for Premix of Sample A

Project: Black Top of Sukute-Chapagaun-Meldanda-Thokarpa-Bhanjyang Road						
Sieve Size Mm	Weight Retained gm	% Retained	Cumulative % Retained	Cumulative % Passing	Specification Limits %	
					Upper	Lower
13.20	0	0.00	0.00	100	100	100
11.20	105	2.10	2.10	97.90	88	100
5.60	2790	55.80	57.90	42.10	31	52
2.80	1368	27.36	83.16	16.80	5	25
0.09	725	14.50	97.66	2.30	0	5
Pan	12	0.24				
Total Weight	5000					

The above gradation analysis of coarse aggregate shown in table complies with close graded premix grading Type B according to Table 13.35 of Standard Specification for Road and Bridge works, 2073. The total aggregates content for above gradation shall be 0.27 m³ per m² area. The binder content for premixing shall be 19.0 kg per 10 m² area. The graph for particle size distribution curve is shown below.

Fig. 4.8 Premix Particle Size Distribution Curve for Sample A

Similarly, Table 4.13 shows complete gradation details of premix chips from Barabise site.

Table 4.13 Gradation of Aggregate for Premix of Sample B

Project: Black Top of Barabise-Thotanaari-Ratamate-Chulthidamar-Ghunde-Om Park Road						
Sieve Size mm	Weight Retained gm	% Retained	Cumulative % Retained	Cumulative % Passing	Specification Limits %	
					Upper	Lower
13.20	0	0.00	0.00	100	100	100
11.20	130	2.60	2.60	97.40	88	100
5.60	2768	55.36	55.36	42.00	31	52
2.80	1385	27.70	83.06	16.90	5	25
0.09	708	14.16	97.22	2.80	0	5
Pan	9	0.18				
Total Weight	5000					

The above gradation analysis of coarse aggregate shown in table complies with close graded premix grading Type B according to Table 13.35 of Standard Specification for Road and Bridge works, 2073. The total aggregates content for above gradation shall be 0.27 m³ per m² area. The binder content for premixing shall be 19.0 kg per 10 m² area. The graph for particle size distribution curve is shown below.

Fig. 4.9 Premix Particle Size Distribution Curve for Sample B

Based on above analysis, it is found that gradation of premix chips aggregate is in compliance with the Standard Specification for Road and Bridge Works, 2073. Hence, the aggregate used dense graded premix has passed physical gradation test.

4.2.3 Los Angeles Abrasion Test

Los Angeles Abrasion test is generally used to determine the abrasive characteristics of the pavement materials. Roadway pavement materials are exposed to significant impact due to dynamic vehicular flow and thus abrasion value of aggregate greatly impact the service life of roadway pavement. Maximum permissible abrasion value as per Standard Specification for Road and Bridge Works 2073 is 30%.

Following tables below shows Los Angeles Abrasion Value of aggregate samples from three different sites.

For Sample A,

Table 4.14 Los Angeles Abrasion Test for Sample A

S.N.	Description	Observed Value
1	Total Weight of Aggregate Sample	5018 gm
2	Weight of Aggregate after abrasion test (500 revolutions) retained on 1.7 mm sieve	3618 gm
3	Weight of Aggregate passing 1.7 mm sieve	1400 gm
4	Ratio of wear Loss %	27.90
Reported LAA Value for Sample A		27.90

Similarly, for Sample B,

Table 4.15 Los Angeles Abrasion Test for Sample B

S.N.	Description	Observed Value
1	Total Weight of Aggregate Sample	5064 gm
2	Weight of Aggregate after abrasion test (500 revolutions) retained on 1.7 mm sieve	3627 gm
3	Weight of Aggregate passing 1.7 mm sieve	1437 gm
4	Ratio of wear Loss %	28.38
Reported LAA Value for Sample B		28.38

Similarly, for Sample C,

Table 4.16 Los Angeles Abrasion Test for Sample C

S.N.	Description	Observed Value
1	Total Weight of Aggregate Sample	5000 gm
2	Weight of Aggregate after abrasion test (500 revolutions) retained on 1.7 mm sieve	3068 gm
3	Weight of Aggregate passing 1.7 mm sieve	1932 gm
4	Ratio of wear Loss %	38.64
Reported LAA Value for Sample C		38.64

Summary for X^2 Test:

Table 4.17 Chi Square Hypothesis Testing for LLA Value

S.N.	Sample	Observed LAA Value	Expected LAA Value	$X^2 = \sum \frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$
		(O)	(E)	
1	A	27.90	30	0.14
2	B	28.38	30	0.08
3	C	38.64	30	2.48
		Total	$X^2 =$	2.70

For, Level of Significance = 5%,

Degree of Freedom = $N-1 = 2$,

Critical Value = 5.99

Decision: Since, $X^2 = 2.70 < 5.99$ (Critical Value). Thus we fail to reject Null Hypothesis H_0 . Hence all road construction sites at Sindhupalchowk District of Province 3, Nepal do achieve required strength of aggregates for base based on Los Angeles Abrasion Value.

Los Angeles Abrasion value for Sample A and Sample B fall within the required quality standard but LAA value for Sample C is beyond the acceptable limit and thus is advised to change the material for base course.

4.2.4 Aggregate Impact Test

The aggregate impact value measures resistance of aggregate to sudden impact which differs from resistance due to compressive load applied gradually. Aggregate impact test specifies minimum strength required to resist the disintegration caused due to impact. Maximum permissible aggregate impact value as per Standard Specification for Road and Bridge Works 2073 is 24%.

Following Table below shows Aggregate Impact Value of aggregate samples from three different sites.

For Sample A,

Table 4.18 Aggregate Impact Value for Sample A

S.N.	Description	Observed Value
A ₁	Weight of Cylindrical Measure + Sample	1384 gm
A ₂	Weight of Cylindrical Measure	1028 gm
A	Weight of Sample (A ₁ - A ₂)	356 gm
B	Weight Passing 2.36 mm Sieve	69 gm
C	Weight Retained on 2.36 mm Sieve	287 gm
D	Total Weight W = B + C	356 gm
Aggregate Impact Value for Sample A		19.38

Similarly, for Sample B,

Table 4.19 Aggregate Impact Value for Sample B

S.N.	Description	Observed Value
A ₁	Weight of Cylindrical Measure + Sample	1419 gm
A ₂	Weight of Cylindrical Measure	1028 gm
A	Weight of Sample (A ₁ - A ₂)	391 gm
B	Weight Passing 2.36 mm Sieve	69 gm
C	Weight Retained on 2.36 mm Sieve	322 gm
D	Total Weight W = B + C	391 gm
Aggregate Impact Value for Sample B		17.65

Similarly, for Sample C,

Table 4.20 Aggregate Impact Value for Sample C

S.N.	Description	Observed Value
A ₁	Weight of Cylindrical Measure + Sample	1170 gm
A ₂	Weight of Cylindrical Measure	836 gm
A	Weight of Sample (A ₁ - A ₂)	334 gm
B	Weight Passing 2.36 mm Sieve	218 gm
C	Weight Retained on 2.36 mm Sieve	116 gm
D	Total Weight W = B + C	334
Aggregate Impact Value for Sample C		34.73

Summary for X^2 Test:

Table 4.21 Chi Square Hypothesis Testing for Aggregate Impact Value

S.N.	Sample	Observed AI Value	Expected AI Value	$X^2 = \sum \frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$
		(O)	(E)	
1	A	19.38	24	0.88
2	B	17.65	24	1.68
3	C	34.73	24	4.79
		Total	$X^2 =$	7.35

For, Level of Significance = 5%,

Degree of Freedom = N-1 = 2,

Critical Value = 5.99

Decision: Since, $X^2 = 7.35 > 5.99$ (Critical Value). Thus we reject Null Hypothesis H₀ and accept alternate Hypothesis H₁. Hence all road construction sites at Sindhupalchowk District of Province 3, Nepal does not achieve required strength of aggregates for base based on Aggregate Impact Value.

Aggregate Impact value for Sample A and Sample B fall within the required quality standard but AI value as well as LAA value for Sample C of Flimcity Access Road is beyond the acceptable limit as specified by Standard Specification for Road and Bridge Works 2073. Thus, the material for base course at Flimcity Access Road is found unfit for use and is advised to change the material for base course.

4.2.5 Core Cutting of Premix Surface

Core cutting of premix surface is performed to verify the thickness of premix surface after compaction as well as determine properties of premix like density, field compaction achieved and so on. Core cutting of premix surface was performed at different sites and thickness was compared with standard thickness to be achieved as per Bill of Quantities of respective contracts. Following Table shows the thickness of premix surface of sites selected for research purpose.

Table 4.22 Core Cutting of Premix Surface at Site A

Project: Black Top of Sukute-Chapagaun-Meldanda-Thokarpa-Bhanjyang Road				
S.N.	No. of Core	Observed Thickness (mm)	Expected Thickness (mm)	$X^2 = \sum \frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$
		(O)	(E)	
1	1	30.83	30	0.02
2	2	31.43	30	0.06
3	3	31.03	30	0.03
4	4	30.22	30	0.00
5	5	31.85	30	0.11
6	6	30.70	30	0.01
7	7	30.85	30	0.02
8	8	30.92	30	0.02
9	9	31.22	30	0.04
10	10	31.65	30	0.09
		Total	$X^2 =$	0.40

For, Level of Significance = 5%,

Degree of Freedom = N-1 = 9,

Critical Value = 18.31

Decision: Since, $X^2 = 0.40 < 18.31$ (Critical Value). Thus we fail to reject Null Hypothesis H_0 . Hence construction work at Black Top of Sukute-Chapagaun-Meldanda-Thokarpa-Bhanjyang Road has maintained minimum premix surface thickness of 30mm throughout its chainage.

Table 4.23 Core Cutting of Premix Surface at Site B

Project: Black Top of Barabise-Thotanaari-Ratamate-Chulthidamar-Ghunde-Om Park Road				
S.N.	No. of Core	Observed Thickness (mm)	Expected Thickness (mm)	$X^2 = \sum \frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$
		(O)	(E)	
1	1	40.67	40	0.01
2	2	40.85	40	0.01
3	3	41.68	40	0.07
4	4	40.82	40	0.01
5	5	40.93	40	0.02
6	6	40.57	40	0.00
7	7	40.97	40	0.02
8	8	41.17	40	0.03
9	9	41.27	40	0.04
10	10	40.72	40	0.01
	Total		$X^2 =$	0.22

For, Level of Significance = 5%,

Degree of Freedom = N-1 = 9,

Critical Value = 18.31

Decision: Since, $X^2 = 0.22 < 18.31$ (Critical Value). Thus we fail to reject Null Hypothesis H_0 . Hence construction work at Black Top of Barabise-Thotanaari-Ratamate-Chulthidamar-Ghunde-Om Park Road has maintained minimum premix surface thickness of 40mm throughout its chainage.

4.3 Significant Risk Factors and their Ranking based on Failure Mode and Effect

Analysis

To identify the significant factors of risk and their ranking for risk priority, respondents were asked to respond for Risk Occurrence (RO), Risk Consequences (RC) and Risk Detectability (RD) for each risk factors based on Crisp Rating from 1 to 5. The average response received for each risk factors is shown in Appendix III. The average response for the risk factors were analyzed to determine Risk Priority Number (RPN) as per FMEA Model and thus risk rank was established. RPN for each risk factor is shown in FMEA table below.

Table 4.24 FMEA Table for the Risk Factors

S.N	Risk Factors	Risk Occurrence		Risk Consequences		Risk Detectability		Risk Priority Number
		ΣW	$ROI = \frac{\Sigma W}{A * N}$	ΣW	$RCI = \frac{\Sigma W}{A * N}$	ΣW	$RDI = \frac{\Sigma W}{A * N}$	$RPN = ROI * RCI * RDI * 100$
1	Project Scope Risk	101.80	0.678	102.40	0.682	97.20	0.648	29.96
2	Design and Specification Risk	100.68	0.671	105.30	0.702	97.05	0.647	30.47
3	Quality Risks	106.05	0.707	103.19	0.687	96.43	0.642	31.18
4	Time Overrun Risk	110.44	0.736	106.83	0.712	107.20	0.714	37.41
5	Cost Overrun Risk	114.20	0.761	107.00	0.713	100.60	0.670	36.35
6	Leadership Risk	101.80	0.678	103.56	0.690	94.69	0.631	29.51
7	Organizational Risk	97.31	0.648	104.35	0.695	104.63	0.697	31.39
8	Physical Resources Mobilization and Utilization Risk	101.81	0.678	101.70	0.678	95.18	0.634	29.14
9	Technology Risk	100.75	0.671	100.25	0.668	99.00	0.660	29.58
10	Contractual Risk	106.08	0.707	97.80	0.652	101.82	0.678	31.25
11	Force Majeure and Ecological Risks	101.94	0.679	104.56	0.697	103.60	0.690	32.65
12	Political Legal and Social Risk	104.00	0.693	104.92	0.699	100.46	0.669	32.4
13	Financial and Economic Risk	107.16	0.714	102.60	0.684	101.17	0.674	32.91
14	Safety Health and Environmental Risk	111.00	0.740	107.00	0.713	105.00	0.700	36.93
15	Communication and Network Failure Risk	95.18	0.634	92.46	0.616	93.08	0.620	24.21

Note: A = 5 (Highest Crisp Rating) & N = 30 (Total Number of Respondent)

FMEA Table 4.23 shows the risk priority number of the given 15 risk factors based on product of Risk Occurrence, Risk Consequences and Risk Detectability. Higher value of RPN shows higher severity of risk factors. Based on the value of RPN, risks are ranked where most severe risk is the one with highest Risk Priority Number. Risk ranking is shown in the table below.

Table 4.25 Risk Ranking of the Risk Factors

S.N.	Risk Factors	Risk Priority Number	Risk Rank
4	Time Overrun Risk	37.41	1
14	Safety Health and Environmental Risk	36.93	2
5	Cost Overrun Risk	36.35	3
13	Financial and Economic Risk	32.91	4
11	Force Majeure and Ecological Risks	32.65	5
12	Political Legal and Social Risk	32.4	6
7	Organizational Risk	31.39	7
10	Contractual Risk	31.25	8
3	Quality Risks	31.18	9
2	Design and Specification Risk	30.47	10
1	Project Scope Risk	29.96	11
9	Technology Risk	29.58	12
6	Leadership Risk	29.51	13
8	Physical Resources Mobilization and Utilization Risk	29.14	14
15	Communication and Network Failure Risk	24.21	15

From Table 4.24, time overrun risk is observed as most severe risk with risk priority number of 37.41. This indicates most of the road construction projects in hilly region suffer from time overrun i.e. project not completing within specified time limit. Inaccurate time estimate, incomplete work breakdown structure, variations and uncertainties, no effective control system are the major causes for this risk factor. Similar study conducted by Mishra and Malik (2017) for housing projects, time overrun risk stands at top rank which shows the uniformity of risk factor irrespective of construction project. Time overrun risk leads to numerous other risk like cost overrun risk, quality risk, ineffective organizational management and so on. Hence, major focus has to be addressed to accurate time estimate and work execution within specified work schedule.

Similarly, Safety Health and Environmental risk stands at second priority risk factor with the priority number of 36.93. Unsafe working condition, accidents, non-conformance to

legislative standards are the reasons for this risk factor. In addition, current global pandemic of COVID-19 is another major reason for increased severity of this risk factor. Safety audit, necessary precaution measure to ensure sound health at work site, adequate disinfection of facilities and social distancing still remains a challenge at construction project of Nepal.

Cost overrun risk and Financial & Economic risk stands at third and fourth priority with priority number 36.35 and 32.91 respectively showing fluctuation and variations in cost estimate as well as market prices. Amount variation is widely seen in road construction projects of Nepal raising doubt in cost estimate of the construction project. Rush bidding and low bidding may be another reason for project not completing within the agreement amount at the time of bidding. Study conducted for housing projects by Mishra and Malik (2017) shows similar result where cost overrun risk stands at second priority.

Since, geology of Sindhupalchowk district is comprised of loose and fragile rock, steep gradient and excessive rainfall, natural disaster like flood and landslide is quite common resulting in huge loss of life, property and infrastructure. Jure Landslide, Melamchi Flood are the magnificent examples which supports fifth risk factor as Force Majeure and Ecological risk with risk priority number of 32.65.

Political Legal and Social risk is the other priority risk with rank sixth and risk priority number 32.4. Constantly changing government policies related to construction activities, legal legislation, Corruption, strike, land acquisition delay, delay in permit and regulation are the major causes for such risk factors. Similarly, dispute among the contracting parties and delay in dispute settlement is next major highlight for such result.

Organizational risk and contractual risk are next in line with priority number of 31.39 and 31.25 respectively. This basically shows management issue within organization and understanding among the contracting parties. Inappropriate organizational network, poor allocation of task and responsibilities, not effective documentation procedure and inadequate communication infrastructure are the major reasons of organizational risk. Similarly, non-standard contract clause, lack of time to finalize bid documents, delay in site possession, payment problems, insufficient documentation of claims and rush bidding are the major reasons of contractual risk occurring in road construction project.

Project specific risk like quality risks, design and specification risks and project scope risk comes at lower priorities with risk priority number of 31.18, 30.47 and 29.96 respectively. This shows project design features and quality in construction are comparatively less important factors affecting the performance of project. Quality risk occur due to absence of quality assurance plan, untrained manpower, poor quality of materials, no soil tests and inadequate quality control methods. Similarly, design and specification risk occurs due to unrealistic specification, probability of design change, difficulties in incorporation of design changes and poor design as a whole. Likewise, high complexity, ill-defined project scope, no extra work control and frequent changing scope requirements are the major cause for project scope risk.

Risk factors based on their weightage of risk priority number can be analyzed through pie chart shown below. This pie chart is typical representation of risk factors based on road construction projects of Sindhupalchowk district, Province 3, Nepal.

Fig 4.10 Weightage of Project Risk Factors

From the pie chart figure 4.10, it is seen that each risk factor has significance impact on output of project. However, risk factors like technological risk, leadership risk, physical resource mobilization and utilization risk as well as communication and network failure risk possess relatively less impact and stand at bottom of risk ranking list. Similar result is seen in study conducted for housing project by Mishra and Malik (2017), where communication and network failure risk is seen at the bottom of risk ranking list.

Cronbach's alpha was calculated to determine the reliability of response collected for significant risk factors. The value of Cronbach's alpha is shown below.

Table 4.26 Reliability Statistics for Significant Risk Factor

S.N.	Parameters	No. of Questions (K)	No. of Respondents (N)	Value of Cronbach's Alpha
1	Risk Occurrence	15	30	0.903
2	Risk Consequences	15	30	0.920
3	Risk Detectability	15	30	0.928

Here, all the values of alpha for response related to significant risk factors are greater than 0.9. Hence, internal consistency of data is excellent.

4.4 Impact of Risk Management Practice on Project Success Criteria

Regression model of hypothesis was tested for the response received through questionnaire survey conducted among the technical employees of the projects within the study area to analyze the impact of risk management practice on the success of construction projects in context of Nepal. Three independent variable were chosen for hypothesis as Risk Identification, Assessment and Response. Top ten success criteria were selected as dependent variable based on risk ranking from FMEA table. Response were collected on Likert scale to analyze the impact of independent variables on various project success criteria.

Response received related to impact of independent variables of risk management practice on project success criteria is shown in Appendix IV. Regression model of hypothesis were tested to find the impact of independent variables on dependent variables and analysis is shown in Appendix V.

Summary of Hypothesis testing is shown in table below.

Table 4.27 Impact of Risk Identification on Project Success

S.N.	Hypothesis	F	Sig F	Impact
1	Impact of Risk Identification on well Planned Project Schedule	5.927	0.022	Impact Exists
2	Impact of Risk Identification on Compliance with Safety Health and Environmental Standards	5.425	0.027	Impact Exists
3	Impact of Risk Identification on Project within the Estimated Budget	1.852	0.184	No Impact Exists
4	Impact of Risk Identification on Well assured Financial and Economic Provisions	10.016	0.004	Impact Exists
5	Impact of Risk Identification on Provision made for Force Majeure Situation	11.760	0.002	Impact Exists
6	Impact of Risk Identification on Compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements	9.992	0.004	Impact Exists
7	Impact of Risk Identification on Well-structured Organizational Management	11.987	0.002	Impact Exists
8	Impact of Risk Identification on No issue in Contractual Arrangement	9.955	0.004	Impact Exists
9	Impact of Risk Identification on Compliance with the Quality Standards	19.344	0.000	Impact Exists
10	Impact of Risk Identification on Compliance with Technical Design Requirements	15.548	0.000	Impact Exists

Table 4.28 Impact of Risk Assessment on Project Success

S.N.	Hypothesis	F	Sig F	Impact
1	Impact of Risk Assessment on well Planned Project Schedule	17.326	0.000	Impact Exists
2	Impact of Risk Assessment on Compliance with Safety Health and Environmental Standards	23.290	0.000	Impact Exists
3	Impact of Risk Assessment on Project within the Estimated Budget	2.109	0.158	No Impact Exists
4	Impact of Risk Assessment on Well assured Financial and Economic Provisions	22.075	0.000	Impact Exists
5	Impact of Risk Assessment on Provision made for Force Majeure Situation	54.194	0.000	Impact Exists
6	Impact of Risk Assessment on Compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements	25.449	0.000	Impact Exists
7	Impact of Risk Assessment on Well-structured Organizational Management	41.404	0.000	Impact Exists
8	Impact of Risk Assessment on No issue in Contractual Arrangement	40.963	0.000	Impact Exists
9	Impact of Risk Assessment on Compliance with the Quality Standards	30.493	0.000	Impact Exists
10	Impact of Risk Assessment on Compliance with Technical Design Requirements	23.614	0.000	Impact Exists

Table 4.29 Impact of Risk Response on Project Success

S.N.	Hypothesis	F	Sig F	Impact
1	Impact of Risk Response on well Planned Project Schedule	19.175	0.000	Impact Exists
2	Impact of Risk Response on Compliance with Safety Health and Environmental Standards	22.928	0.000	Impact Exists
3	Impact of Risk Response on Project within the Estimated Budget	8.323	0.007	Impact Exists
4	Impact of Risk Response on Well assured Financial and Economic Provisions	36.210	0.000	Impact Exists
5	Impact of Risk Response on Provision made for Force Majeure Situation	15.752	0.000	Impact Exists
6	Impact of Risk Response on Compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements	23.699	0.000	Impact Exists
7	Impact of Risk Response on Well-structured Organizational Management	17.539	0.000	Impact Exists

8	Impact of Risk Response on No issue in Contractual Arrangement	4.381	0.046	Impact Exists
9	Impact of Risk Response on Compliance with the Quality Standards	28.142	0.000	Impact Exists
10	Impact of Risk Response on Compliance with Technical Design Requirements	23.805	0.000	Impact Exists

Discussion on result of Hypothesis Testing:

The parameters of Risk management (Risk Identification, Risk Assessment and Risk Response) was found to lay a considerable impact on project success. Numerous risk factors were considered that were likely to occur in the road construction projects and risk were ranked to select top ten risk factors. Success criteria were constructed based on top risk factors and impact was analyzed through regression model of hypothesis testing. Impact of Risk Identification, Risk Assessment and Risk Response on project success criteria were observed in following manner.

1. Risk Identification, Risk Assessment and Risk Response was found to have a significant impact on well planned project schedule. Early identification of inaccurate activity time estimate, improper work breakdown and project schedule and inflexible project schedule helps to take necessary analysis and assessment of risk as well as take appropriate risk response plan. This helps to reduce the consequences of risk on project output ensuring timely completion of project.
2. Risk Identification, Risk Assessment and Risk Response was found to have a significant impact on compliance with safety, health and environmental standard. Risk consequence on human health is quite impactful as compared with other risk factors. It affects both life and property of personnel involved in construction activities. Current condition of global pandemic COVID-19 has put a great challenge on construction activities. Identification of relevant risk factors that are not in compliance with legislative standards highlights the potential risk along with its severity and scale of impact. Adequate assessment and appropriate risk response strategy is quite essential to ensure the success of project.
3. Risk Identification was found to not have significant impact on project within the estimated budget. As long as project proceeds within its allocated budget, there exists no impact on cost overrun risk. Similarly, Risk Assessment was found to play non-significant role in project success related to budget. However, the risk response of the relevant risk factors plays very significant role in the budget of project. Appropriate risk response strategy to carry the progress of project within the planned budget appeared to be very significant for ensuring success of project.

4. Risk Identification, Risk Assessment and Risk Response was found to have a significant impact on well assured financial and economic provisions. Project budget is one of the most important factor that requires constant monitoring and control. To ensure uniform and adequate cash flows as and when needed as well as justify economically is very critical to deliver the output of project successfully. Thus, identification of risks, their assessment and appropriate risk response plan ensures project success based on financial and economic parameters.
5. Risk Identification, Risk Assessment and Risk Response was found to have a significant impact on provisions made for force majeure situation. Geology of Sindhupalchowk district is comprised of loose and fragile rock with constant large scale landslide. Further, huge rainfall often leads to devastating floods during monsoon season. These effects had constantly increased risks of force majeure situation and thus the impact of risk management parameters was found significant on project success.
6. Risk Identification, Risk Assessment and Risk Response was found to have a significant impact on compliance with political, legal and social requirements. Unstable politics, frequently changing governmental policies, unstable market and social conflict due to difference in interest has brought large impact on construction efficiency, often being reason of work stoppage. Thus, a project, for its success, identification, assessment and response of such risk factors is quite essential.
7. Risk Identification, Risk Assessment and Risk Response was found to have a significant impact on well-structured organizational management. Management of construction organization is a complex job with numerous staff and multiple department. Poor allocation of task and responsibilities, unrealistic project expectation, selection of wrong project, inflexible project plan, adequate resource not available and no proper documentation system leads to failure of project due to organizational management risk. Thus, risk management has high impact on project success.
8. Risk Identification, Risk Assessment and Risk Response was found to have a significant impact on issue on contractual agreement. Non-standard condition of contract, delay in possession of site, lack of time to prepare bids, errors/omission in BOQ, no proper documentation of disputes and claims, lack of insurance, rush bidding and payment problems can be potential risk factors related to contractual issue. Thus, risk management parameters have significant impact on contractual issue.
9. Risk Identification, Risk Assessment and Risk Response was found to have a significant impact on compliance with quality standard. Absence of QAP, untrained manpower, poor material quality and unachievable quality standards were the quality related issue that could risk the success of project. Thus, risk management parameters have significant impact on quality issues.

10. Risk Identification, Risk Assessment and Risk Response was found to have a significant impact on compliance with technical design and specification requirements. Inadequate design information, incorporation of new construction technology, unrealistic specification, likelihood of design changes, difficulties in interaction of design changes, non-conformity with national standards and local specifications, inaccurate quantities are the design risk that has potential to impact the success of project. Thus, risk management parameters have significant impact on compliance with technical design requirements.

To test the reliability of significant risk factors, Cronbach's alpha was calculated to determine the internal consistency.

Table 4.30 Reliability Statistics for Impact on Project Success Criteria

S.N.	Parameters	No. of Questions (K)	No. of Respondents (N)	Value of Cronbach's Alpha
1	Risk Identification	10	30	0.935
2	Risk Assessment	10	30	0.928
3	Risk Response	10	30	0.947

Here, all the values of alpha for responses related to impact of risk management practice on project success is greater than 0.9. Hence, internal consistency of data is found to be excellent.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study was carried out to analyze the practice of risk management followed for road construction projects at Sindhupalchowk district, Province 3, Nepal. The adopted practice was analyzed based on client's and contractor's perspective. Lab tests were performed to check the conformance of work proceeds with the required quality standards.

The focus of study was ranking of the various risk factors based on its severity. Risk factors were ascertained based on relevant literatures and key informant interview. Ranking of the risk factors was done through its score on occurrence, consequences and detectability.

The study also analyzed the impact of risk management practice on success of the project. Success criteria were obtained through top risk factors based on its ranking. Impact of Risk Identification, Risk Assessment and Risk Response on those success criteria was analyzed through regression model of hypothesis testing.

5.1 Conclusion

Risk management practice based on contractor's perspective shows average awareness of management with mean score of 3.30. Further, managements are found averagely practicing risk management formally or informally with mean score of 3.03. The study shows slight decrease in score for risk management being practiced formally with mean score of 2.83. It is also found that managements are averagely analyzing risk management techniques with mean score of 3.07. Based on contractor's perspective, mostly adopted techniques for risk identification are expert opinion and monitoring and evaluation report of similar past projects. Direct judgment is widely used technique for risk assessment of road construction projects at Sindhupalchowk district. Similarly, monitoring the risk and preparing contingency plan is the mostly adopted risk response strategy by contractors of Sindhupalchowk district.

The study of management awareness regarding risk management practice based on client's perspective shows slightly higher score with mean score of 3.93. Further, managements are found averagely practicing risk management formally or informally with mean score of 3.33. The study shows slight decrease in score for risk management being practiced formally with mean score of 3.13. It is also found that managements are averagely analyzing risk management techniques with mean score of 3.40. Based on client's perspective, mostly adopted techniques for Risk Identification is monitoring and evaluation report of similar past projects. Direct judgment is also widely used technique by client for risk assessment of road construction projects at Sindhupalchowk district. Similarly, transfer of risk is the mostly used risk response strategy by clients of Sindhupalchowk district.

The research also focuses on conformance of quality of material used in road construction with the required quality standards. Based on test reports, it is observed that materials being used for base course and premix chip meet the required gradation limits. Similarly, Los Angeles Abrasion test and Aggregate Impact Value test results also falls within the specified

limit as set by Standard Specification for Road and Bridge Works. These value for a single site was found beyond acceptable limit and was advised for replacement of base material. Core cutting result of pavement surface shows adequacy in thickness of premix surface which gives the ideology that required quality parameters are being achieved in the road construction projects.

This research also evaluates significant risk factors and its ranking for road construction project. Time overrun risk is the most significant risk factor with highest severity. Similarly, Safety Health and Environmental risk, Cost overrun risk, Financial and Economic risk, Force Majeure and Ecological risk, Political Legal and Social risk, Organizational risk, Contractual risk, Quality Risks and Design and Specification risk are the significant risk factors based on descending order of risk priority number as per FMEA Model. Other risk factors include Project Scope risk, Technology risk, Leadership risk, Physical Resource Mobilization and Utilization risk and Communication and Network Failure risk that stands at bottom of the ranking list in case of road construction projects of Nepal.

All the three independent variables of Risk Management Practice (Risk Identification, Risk Assessment and Risk Response) have significant impact on nine out of ten success criteria as well planned project schedule, compliance with Safety Health and Environmental standards, well assured financial and economic provisions, provision made for force majeure situation, compliance with Political Legal and Social requirements, well-structured organizational management, no issue in contractual agreement, compliance with quality standards and compliance with technical design requirements. For the remaining success criteria, project within estimated budget, Risk Identification and Risk Assessment have no impact whereas Risk Response has significant impact. Hence, even one fails to identify risk, if appropriate Risk Response strategy is selected, success of project can be insured.

5.2 Recommendation

- Training should be conducted for contractor's management related to formal techniques of risk management practice.
- Risk register should be maintained at site and updated on regular basis. Meetings among stakeholders should be conducted to identify the significant risk factors.
- Training should be conducted for client's and contractor's management for Risk Assessment through Sensitivity, Scenario and Simulation Analysis.
- Lab Tests should be conducted to check the conformance of quality of materials used at construction site with the desired quality standards.
- To manage the risk effectively and efficiently, organization should focus on its occurrence, its consequences as well as its detectability.

5.3 Proposed future studies

It is recommended for the researchers who are interested to conduct thesis work in Risk Management field can study on:

- Risk Management Practice in Nation Highway construction project in Nepal.
- Risk Management Practice in building construction project in Nepal.
- Challenges for road contractors to follow formal risk management methods in Nepalese context.
- Improvement required for road contractors in Risk Management practice.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX I
Questionnaire Survey

Part-1

General/Organizational Information

This research survey is designed to fulfill an academic requirement for an **M.Sc. program in Construction Management at Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal, Pokhara University**. I can assure you that the research data will only be used for academic purposes. Particular mentioning of name will not be required anywhere. Your open and prompt response is highly appreciated.

- 1) Name of Construction Company/ Consultant/ Client (Owner):
- 2) Position of respondent:
- 3) Qualification of the respondent:
- 4) Experience of the respondent:

Part-2

A. Questionnaire related to Risk Management Practice:

- 1) **To what extent, the top management of your organization is aware of the Risk Management Practice?**
(1- Least Aware to 5- Most Aware)
- 2) **How much Risk Management Practice (formally or informally) is being followed in your project?**
(1- Least Practice to 5-Most Practice)
- 3) **How much formal techniques of Risk Management (Risk Identification, Risk Assessment, Risk Response Plan) are applied in the project?**
(1- Least Formal techniques to 5- Most Formal techniques)
- 4) **How much risk analyzing techniques are used in the project?**
(1-Least used to 5- Most used)
- 5) **How do you identify potential risk of the project?**
 - a) Contract document
 - b) Risk Register
 - c) Expert Opinion
 - d) Brainstorming
 - e) Monitoring and Evaluation Report of similar past projects
 - f) Others

6) How do you analyze risk of the project?

- a) Direct Judgment
- b) Ranking Options
- c) Comparative analysis
- d) Descriptive analysis
- e) Probability analysis
- f) Sensitive analysis
- g) Scenario analysis
- h) Simulation analysis
- i) Others

7) How do you respond to risk of the project?

- a) Accepting the risk
- b) Avoiding the risk
- c) Monitoring the risk and preparing Contingency Plan
- d) Transferring the risk
- e) Mitigating the risk
- f) Others

B. Questionnaire to analyze Risk factors and their Severity:

From the below list of various risk factors, rate the Probability of Risk Occurrence(RO); Risk Consequences(RC) and Risk Detectability(RD) from 1 to 5 where:

Table 6.1 Linguistic Definition for Numerical Rating

Numerical Rating	Linguistic Term	Linguistic Definition	
5	Very High	RO	Risk has high certainty of occurrence.
		RC	Extreme consequences, unable to meet project goal.
		RD	Very less chances of discovering risk prior it does any harm.
4	High	RO	Risk is expected to occur.
		RC	Major consequences affecting most part of project goal.
		RD	Less chances of discovering risk prior it does any harm.
3	Medium	RO	Risk may occur.
		RC	Medium consequences, affecting small part of project output.
		RD	Medium chances of discovering risk prior it does any harm.
2	Low	RO	Risk is unlikely to occur.
		RC	Few consequences, project outputs are slightly affected.
		RD	Good chances of risk to be detected prior it does any harm.
1	Very Low	RO	Risk is highly unlikely to occur.
		RC	Negligible consequences, project outputs are met.
		RD	Very high chances of discovering risk prior it does any harm.

Table 6.2 Risk Factors

S.N	Risk factors	Risk Occurrence	Risk Consequences	Risk Detectability
1	Project Scope Risks			
	1 High Complexity			
	2 Ill- defined project scope			
	3 Frequent changing scope requirements			
	4 No extra work control			
	5 No analysis of changes in problem			
2	Design and Specification Risk			
	1 Inadequate design information			
	2 Incorporation of new construction technology			
	3 Unrealistic specification			
	4 Likelihood of design changes			
	5 Difficulties in interaction of design changes			
	6 Poor design			
	7 Non-conformity with national standard and local specifications			
	8 Inaccurate quantities			
3	Quality Risks			
	1 No Quality Assurance Plan			
	2 No soil investigation			
	3 No method statement			
	4 Poor quality materials			
	5 Untrained manpower			
	6 Lack of soil and material testing laboratories			
	7 Unachievable quality control			
	8 Problem in quality control			
4	Time Overrun Risk			
	1 Inaccurate activity time estimates			

	2	Unrealistic time schedules			
	3	Incomplete WBS			
	4	No formal sequencing plan			
	5	Inaccurate estimation of project schedule, resources and quality assurance plans			
	6	Inefficient control system			
	7	Inflexible & unrealistic project goals			
	8	Inability to take timely the corrective action			
5	Cost Overrun Risks				
	1	Inaccurate cost estimates			
	2	Inadequate cost control planning			
	3	No control of extra work			
	4	Constantly change market conditions			
	5	Delay payment on contract			
6	Leadership Risks				
	1	Lack of project vision			
	2	Lack of team building			
	3	Poor motivation of stakeholders			
	4	High turnover of critical team members			
	5	Unrealistic expectation			
	6	Poor communication			
	7	High rate of sickness and absenteeism			
	8	Absence of safe working condition resulting site accidents			
7	Organizational Risks				
	1	Inappropriate organizational framework			
	2	Poor assignment/allocation of tasks and responsibilities			

	3	No project manual/ documented procedures			
	4	Project being too complex for the resources available			
	5	Inadequate communication infrastructure			
	6	Wrong selection of project management			
	7	Inflexible and unrealistic project plans			
8	Physical Resources Mobilization and Utilization Risks				
	1	Inadequate and low quality procurement of resources			
	2	Special equipment and materials, transport delay			
	3	Low productivity			
	4	Bad weather and working condition			
	5	Damage during construction due to negligence			
	6	Accidents			
	7	Waste			
	8	Thief and Fraud			
9	Technology Risks				
	1	Inadequate information on new technology			
	2	Non- replacement of old technology			
	3	Non-availability of competent and professional staff to use new technology			
	4	Lack of managerial skills			
10	Contractual Risks				
	1	Non-standard condition of contract			
	2	Lack of time to prepare bid document			
	3	Delay in site possession			
	4	Errors/omission in BOQ			
	5	Payment issues			

	6	Lack of insurance			
	7	No documentation of claims/disputes			
	8	Rush bidding			
11	Force Majeure and Ecological Risks				
	1	Act of god such as earthquake , floods, landslide, etc.			
	2	Ecological damage			
	3	Epidemics			
12	Political , legal and social risk				
	1	Change in government, policies, regulations, rules , laws			
	2	Local regulation			
	3	Crime and insecurity			
	4	Corruption			
	5	Land acquisition delay			
	6	Strike			
	7	Permits and regulations			
	8	Dispute among parties			
	9	Delay in dispute resolutions			
13	Financial and Economic Risk				
	1	Investment risks			
	2	Inflation			
	3	Escalation of prices			
	4	Local and national taxes			
	5	Cash flow problem			
	6	Effect of time and cost overrun			
	7	Demand scenario and constantly changing market conditions			
14	Safety , Health and Environmental Risk				
	1	Unsafe working condition			
	2	Pandemics and Viral Infection (like COVID-19)			

	3	Non- conformance Safety Health and Environmental requirements			
	4	Accident/ Strikes/ work stoppage and worker perceptions			
	5	Absence of safety audit			
15	Communication and network failure risks				
	1	Non availability of anti-virus software to safeguard office computers			
	2	Loss of data due to network problem			
	3	No backup of data available			
	4	Lack of resources			
	5	High electricity fluctuation			
	6	Internet server breakdown			
	7	Ineffective information management system			

C. Questionnaire to analyze the impact of Risk Management Practice:

From the below list of various success criteria, rate the impact of Risk Identification; Assessment and Response on project success from 1 to 5 where “1- Very Low, 2- Low & 3- Medium, 4- High & 5- Very High”

Table 6.3 Project Success Criteria

S. N.	Project Success Criteria	Independent Variables		
		Risk Identification	Risk Assessment	Risk Response
1	Well Defined Project Scope			
2	Compliance with Technical Design Requirements			
3	Compliance with the Quality Standards			
4	Well Planned Project Schedule			
5	Project within the Estimated Budget			
6	Competent Leadership Skill			
7	Well-structured Organizational Management			
8	Adequate Physical Resource			
9	Use of Adequate Technological Infrastructure			
10	No issue in Contractual Arrangement			
11	Provision made for Force Majeure Situation			
12	Compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements			
13	Well assured Financial and Economic Provisions			
14	Compliance with Safety Health and Environmental Standards			
15	Well-structured Communication Plan and better Team Coordination			

APPENDIX II
RESPONSE RELATED TO RISK MANAGEMENT PRACTICE

Table 6.4 Response related to Risk Management Practice, Contractor's Perspective

No. of Respondent	1) To what extent, the top management of your organization is aware of the Risk Management Practice?	2) How much Risk Management Practice (formally or informally) is being followed in your project?	3) How much formal techniques of Risk Management (Risk Identification, Risk Assessment, Risk Response Plan) are applied in the project?	4) How much risk analyzing techniques are used in the project?	5) How do you identify potential risk of the project?	6) How do you analyze risk of the project?	7) How do you respond to risk of the project?
1	4	3	3	4	A,C,E	A,B,C	B,C
2	3	3	2	3	C	A	A
3	3	2	2	3	E	A	C
4	3	3	2	2	C	A,D	B
5	4	4	3	4	E	A	C
6	3	3	2	3	C	A	E
7	4	3	3	4	C,E	A,C	E
8	3	3	3	4	B	A,C,D	C,D
9	3	3	3	3	E	A	E
10	2	2	2	3	E	A,C	C,E
11	4	3	3	3	E	A,C,E	C
12	3	3	3	2	E	A	D
13	3	3	3	2	E	A	C
14	3	3	3	3	C,D,E	A,D	C,D
15	4	4	4	4	E	A,C	C
16	4	4	4	4	C	A,E	C
17	3	3	2	2	C	A	A
18	3	3	3	4	C,E	A,C	B,C
19	3	3	3	3	E	C	C
20	3	3	4	3	A,C,D,E	C,D	C,E
21	4	4	3	3	C	C,E	C
22	3	3	3	3	E	A,C	B,C
23	4	3	2	2	E	E	C,E
24	4	3	3	3	C	A	C
25	3	3	3	3	C	D	D
26	3	3	3	4	C,E	C,D	B
27	3	3	3	3	C,E	C	E
28	4	3	3	3	A,C,D	A	C
29	3	2	3	2	C,D,E	A,B	C,D
30	3	3	2	3	C	A,D	B,C

Table 6.5 Response related to Risk Management Practice, Client’s Perspective

No. of Respondent	1) To what extent, the top management of your organization is aware of the Risk Management Practice?	2) How much Risk Management Practice (formally or informally) is being followed in your project?	3) How much formal techniques of Risk Management (Risk Identification, Risk Assessment, Risk Response Plan) are applied in the project?	4) How much risk analyzing techniques are used in the project?	5) How do you identify potential risk of the project?	6) How do you analyze risk of the project?	7) How do you respond to risk of the project?
1	5	4	3	3	A,E	A,C	D
2	4	3	3	3	E	A,B	B,D
3	4	4	3	4	C,D,E	A,B	C,D
4	3	3	3	3	A,C	A,B	D
5	4	4	4	4	A,E	A	D
6	4	3	3	3	C,E	A,B,C	C,D
7	4	3	3	3	C,E	A,C	B,D
8	3	3	3	4	C,E,D	A,C,E	B,D
9	5	4	4	4	A,E	A,B	D
10	4	3	3	3	D,E	A,E	C,D
11	4	3	3	3	A,E	A	C,D
12	3	3	3	3	E	A	D
13	4	3	3	4	E	A,B,E	B,D
14	3	3	3	3	C,E	A	C,D
15	5	4	3	4	D,E	A	D

APPENDIX III
RESPONSE RELATED TO FMEA MODEL

Table 6.6 Average Response for Risk Occurrence of the Risk Factors

No. of Respondent	Project Scope Risk	Design and Specification Risk	Quality Risks	Time Overrun Risk	Cost Overrun Risk	Leadership Risk	Organizational Risk	Physical Resources Mobilization and Utilization Risk	Technology Risk	Contractual Risk	Force Majeure and Ecological Risks	Political Legal and Social Risk	Financial and Economic Risk	Safety Health and Environmental Risk	Communication and Network Failure Risk
1	3.00	2.75	3.12	3.87	4.00	3.25	1.85	3.00	3.50	3.75	3.00	3.88	3.71	4.60	3.14
2	3.20	3.00	3.00	3.50	3.20	3.25	3.57	2.87	3.00	2.75	3.33	3.22	2.85	3.20	3.14
3	3.40	3.87	4.00	3.75	3.60	4.50	3.57	4.00	3.75	4.00	3.66	3.88	3.85	3.60	3.28
4	3.20	2.12	3.50	3.25	3.40	3.50	3.42	3.37	3.25	3.87	4.00	4.33	4.57	3.80	3.71
5	3.80	3.62	4.12	4.00	4.40	3.87	3.42	3.87	4.75	3.87	3.33	3.66	4.28	4.40	3.57
6	3.60	3.37	3.87	3.62	3.40	4.12	4.00	3.50	3.50	3.50	3.00	3.88	3.85	4.40	3.71
7	3.60	3.00	3.12	3.37	3.40	2.62	3.14	3.12	3.50	3.50	3.33	3.44	3.14	3.40	3.14
8	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
9	3.60	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00
10	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.80	3.87	3.71	3.62	3.75	4.12	4.00	4.11	3.00	4.00	3.00
11	3.40	3.62	3.62	3.50	3.20	2.62	2.42	3.25	2.50	3.00	3.00	2.55	2.85	3.00	2.14
12	3.80	4.00	3.50	4.50	4.40	4.12	4.00	3.75	3.25	3.50	3.66	3.55	3.71	3.60	3.57
13	4.00	3.87	4.00	4.00	3.60	3.87	3.71	3.87	4.25	5.00	3.66	3.66	3.71	4.00	3.85
14	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00

15	3.00	3.62	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
16	4.00	3.87	3.87	3.50	3.20	3.75	3.57	3.37	3.25	3.25	3.33	3.22	3.14	3.40	3.14
17	3.80	4.00	4.37	4.37	4.20	3.37	3.85	3.62	3.00	3.50	2.33	2.55	3.00	2.80	2.42
18	3.20	3.62	3.37	3.62	3.60	3.50	3.57	3.12	3.25	3.62	3.00	3.00	3.14	3.20	3.28
19	2.60	2.50	2.12	2.37	3.40	2.87	1.85	2.50	2.75	1.87	3.00	2.55	2.57	2.60	1.42
20	4.20	4.25	4.37	3.37	4.40	3.87	3.85	4.00	4.25	3.87	4.00	4.22	4.00	4.20	3.42
21	3.20	3.62	3.87	4.37	4.00	2.62	2.42	3.12	2.75	3.75	4.00	3.22	4.25	4.20	3.57
22	3.80	3.00	3.50	4.00	4.60	3.25	3.00	4.00	3.50	3.87	3.33	4.33	3.71	4.00	3.00
23	3.60	3.87	3.62	4.50	3.60	3.00	3.71	2.87	3.25	3.50	3.66	3.44	4.57	4.60	2.42
24	3.00	2.75	4.00	3.87	4.20	3.25	3.14	3.00	3.00	4.00	3.33	4.11	4.00	3.00	3.14
25	3.20	3.62	3.12	3.75	4.00	2.62	3.42	3.75	3.75	4.12	4.00	4.00	4.28	4.40	3.28
26	3.00	2.50	3.50	4.50	4.20	4.12	1.85	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.33	3.22	3.85	4.60	3.14
27	3.40	3.87	4.37	3.87	4.40	3.25	3.71	3.87	3.25	3.25	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.40	3.00
28	3.20	3.00	4.00	4.00	4.80	2.62	4.00	3.50	3.75	4.12	4.00	3.55	3.71	3.20	3.85
29	3.40	3.62	3.12	3.62	4.00	3.87	2.42	3.25	2.50	2.75	3.00	2.55	3.14	4.00	3.14
30	3.60	2.75	3.00	3.37	3.20	3.25	3.14	3.62	3.50	3.75	3.66	3.88	4.28	4.40	3.71
Sum Of Resp onses Σw	101. 80	100.68	106.05	110.4 4	114. 20	101.8 0	97.31	101.81	100.7 5	106.08	101.94	104.00	107.16	111.00	95.18

Table 6.7 Average Response for Risk Consequences of the Risk Factors

No. of Respondent	Project Scope Risk	Design and Specification Risk	Quality Risks	Time Overrun Risk	Cost Overrun Risk	Leadership Risk	Organizational Risk	Physical Resources Mobilization and Utilization Risk	Technology Risk	Contractual Risk	Force Majeure and Ecological Risks	Political Legal and Social Risk	Financial and Economic Risk	Safety Health and Environmental Risk	Communication and Network Failure Risk
1	3.60	3.12	3.50	3.12	4.80	3.12	3.00	3.25	2.75	2.50	3.66	4.11	3.42	3.40	2.14
2	4.00	3.12	3.12	3.50	3.40	3.00	3.57	3.37	3.50	3.12	3.33	3.33	3.28	3.00	3.00
3	3.40	3.50	3.37	3.75	4.80	4.25	4.00	3.87	3.50	3.50	3.66	3.44	3.42	3.80	3.57
4	3.00	3.37	3.75	4.00	2.60	2.37	2.28	3.50	3.50	4.12	5.00	5.00	3.57	3.80	2.71
5	4.00	4.25	4.25	4.50	4.00	4.00	4.57	4.37	4.00	4.50	3.66	4.00	4.00	4.40	3.57
6	3.80	3.62	3.75	3.75	3.80	3.62	3.71	3.50	3.75	3.62	3.33	3.88	3.42	3.80	3.85
7	3.40	3.12	3.12	3.25	3.20	3.12	3.42	3.37	3.50	2.87	3.66	3.11	3.42	3.20	3.42
8	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
9	3.40	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	3.71
10	3.00	4.00	3.50	4.00	4.00	3.37	3.57	3.50	3.75	3.00	5.00	4.00	3.00	3.80	3.00
11	2.80	2.75	2.50	2.62	3.00	2.12	1.71	1.87	2.25	2.12	2.66	2.22	2.57	3.00	2.42
12	3.60	3.62	3.62	3.75	3.60	3.62	4.57	4.12	3.75	3.87	3.66	3.88	3.85	3.60	3.71
13	4.00	4.12	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.25	4.57	4.00	3.75	4.12	4.00	4.00	3.42	4.40	3.42
14	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00

15	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
16	3.80	4.00	3.50	3.37	3.20	3.25	3.28	3.00	3.25	3.25	3.33	3.22	3.14	3.20	3.14
17	4.00	3.62	3.62	3.62	3.80	3.00	3.57	3.62	3.75	3.50	2.66	3.44	3.57	3.60	3.00
18	3.20	3.37	3.25	4.00	3.40	3.62	4.00	3.00	3.50	3.50	3.00	3.00	3.28	3.40	3.28
19	2.80	3.00	2.50	3.25	2.40	2.75	2.00	2.25	3.00	2.62	2.66	2.33	2.57	2.80	2.85
20	3.40	4.75	4.75	3.87	4.00	4.75	4.14	4.50	3.75	3.75	4.66	3.88	4.14	3.40	2.57
21	3.60	3.12	3.62	3.75	3.80	3.62	3.57	3.37	2.75	2.50	3.66	3.33	4.00	3.80	2.85
22	4.00	3.50	3.12	4.00	4.00	4.25	2.28	3.50	3.00	3.12	3.33	4.11	3.28	4.40	2.57
23	3.80	3.37	3.37	4.25	3.80	3.12	3.42	3.00	3.50	3.50	2.66	3.00	3.42	3.20	3.00
24	3.00	3.62	4.25	3.87	3.60	4.00	3.57	3.25	3.75	3.12	3.66	3.88	3.85	3.00	3.57
25	3.40	3.00	3.12	3.62	2.60	3.37	4.00	4.00	3.50	4.12	3.00	4.11	3.42	3.80	2.71
26	3.60	4.00	3.62	3.75	4.00	4.00	3.57	3.37	3.50	2.50	4.00	3.11	3.28	4.40	3.71
27	2.80	4.25	3.75	3.25	3.80	3.12	3.71	3.00	3.00	2.87	3.00	3.88	4.00	4.40	2.42
28	3.00	3.12	3.62	2.62	4.00	3.62	3.42	4.12	3.75	2.87	2.66	3.44	3.14	3.80	3.14
29	3.40	3.37	2.50	3.25	3.40	3.00	4.57	3.00	3.00	4.12	3.66	3.00	3.00	3.40	3.28
30	3.60	3.62	3.12	3.12	3.00	4.25	3.28	3.00	2.25	2.12	4.00	3.22	4.14	3.20	2.85
Sum Of Resp ponses Σw	102. 40	105.30	103.19	106.8 3	107. 00	103.5 6	104.35	101.70	100.2 5	97.80	104.56	104.92	102.60	107.00	92.46

Table 6.8 Average Response for Risk Detectability of the Risk Factors

No. of Respondent	Project Scope Risk	Design and Specification Risk	Quality Risks	Time Overrun Risk	Cost Overrun Risk	Leadership Risk	Organizational Risk	Physical Resources Mobilization and Utilization Risk	Technology Risk	Contractual Risk	Force Majeure and Ecological Risks	Political Legal and Social Risk	Financial and Economic Risk	Safety Health and Environmental Risk	Communication and Network Failure Risk
1	3.20	2.12	2.62	3.50	3.60	2.50	3.00	3.00	3.25	3.37	4.33	3.55	3.28	3.60	2.00
2	3.00	3.37	3.25	3.62	2.60	3.50	3.28	3.00	3.50	3.62	3.00	3.33	3.14	3.40	3.57
3	3.40	3.37	3.37	3.50	3.40	3.37	4.85	4.00	4.00	4.00	3.00	4.00	3.71	3.80	4.00
4	4.00	3.87	3.62	4.25	3.40	3.50	4.57	3.37	3.00	3.87	4.00	3.66	3.57	3.60	3.71
5	4.20	4.12	4.62	4.75	4.40	4.12	4.71	4.00	4.75	4.12	4.00	4.44	4.42	4.40	3.28
6	3.60	3.62	3.75	3.62	3.60	3.62	3.71	3.50	3.50	3.62	3.66	3.66	3.42	3.80	3.57
7	3.40	2.75	2.87	3.25	3.00	3.25	3.57	2.87	3.25	2.87	3.33	3.33	3.57	3.40	3.28
8	2.80	3.50	3.25	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	2.87	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
9	3.40	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00
10	3.00	3.50	3.37	3.37	3.00	3.37	3.42	3.37	3.25	3.50	4.00	3.22	3.42	3.40	3.14
11	2.00	2.00	2.12	2.37	2.40	1.87	1.57	2.12	2.25	3.00	2.33	2.66	2.57	3.00	2.00
12	3.60	3.75	3.75	3.87	3.60	3.87	4.42	3.62	3.50	3.62	4.00	4.55	4.14	4.00	2.85
13	3.00	3.75	3.37	4.00	4.00	3.75	3.71	3.62	4.00	4.25	4.00	4.11	4.28	3.80	3.28
14	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00

15	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
16	3.80	3.62	3.75	3.37	3.00	3.25	3.28	3.00	3.25	3.00	3.00	3.22	3.14	3.20	2.28
17	3.60	3.62	3.62	3.25	3.80	3.50	3.71	3.50	3.75	3.75	3.00	2.66	3.57	3.40	3.28
18	3.40	3.37	3.37	3.75	3.20	3.87	4.14	2.87	3.00	3.50	3.00	3.00	3.28	3.40	3.00
19	2.60	3.00	2.75	2.37	2.60	2.62	2.00	2.50	2.75	2.50	3.00	2.44	2.42	3.00	3.00
20	2.60	1.87	3.00	2.62	3.00	2.87	2.57	3.87	3.00	3.25	4.33	2.44	2.14	3.60	3.00
21	3.20	2.12	3.00	3.50	4.00	2.62	3.00	3.00	3.25	3.37	4.33	3.33	3.28	3.60	3.57
22	3.00	3.37	2.62	3.62	3.60	2.50	4.71	3.37	2.25	3.62	3.00	3.55	3.14	3.00	2.00
23	3.20	2.75	3.00	4.25	4.40	3.00	3.00	3.50	3.50	3.00	3.66	3.00	3.28	3.60	3.00
24	3.40	4.00	2.87	4.75	3.60	3.50	4.14	2.87	3.25	2.87	3.00	3.66	3.57	3.00	3.71
25	3.20	3.75	2.62	4.00	3.80	2.50	3.28	2.12	3.00	4.25	4.00	3.55	3.00	4.00	3.00
26	3.00	2.75	3.25	3.62	4.00	3.25	3.00	3.37	3.25	3.00	3.30	4.11	3.28	3.80	3.57
27	4.20	2.00	3.00	4.25	3.60	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.75	3.62	3.00	3.33	4.42	3.60	2.00
28	3.00	3.62	3.25	3.75	2.40	2.87	3.71	2.87	3.00	3.00	3.33	2.44	3.42	3.20	3.28
29	2.60	3.37	3.00	3.25	2.60	2.62	3.28	3.00	3.50	3.25	4.00	3.22	3.57	3.80	3.00
30	3.80	4.12	3.37	3.75	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.25	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.14	3.60	3.71
Sum Of Resp onses Σw	97.2 0	97.05	96.43	107.2 0	100. 60	94.69	104.6 3	95.18	99.0 0	101.8 2	103.6 0	100.4 6	101. 17	105.00	93.08

APPENDIX IV
Response Related to Project Success Criteria

Table 6.9 Response Related to Impact of Risk Identification on Project Success Criteria

No. of Respondent	Well Planned Project Schedule	Compliance with Safety Health and Environmental Standards	Project within the Estimated Budget	Well assured Financial and Economic Provisions	Provision made for Force Majeure Situation	Compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements	Well-structured Organizational Management	No issue in Contractual Arrangement	Compliance with the Quality Standards	Compliance with Technical Design Requirements	Mean Response on Project Success
1	5	3	5	4	3	3	3	2	4	4	3.63
2	4	4	3	4	3	5	5	4	4	4	4.20
3	4	4	3	4	4	3	3	4	4	3	3.73
4	4	4	4	3	3	4	3	4	5	4	3.73
5	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	5	5	4.03
6	3	3	4	4	4	3	4	3	4	3	3.50
7	4	4	4	3	3	4	2	4	3	4	3.23
8	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	2.96
9	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5.00
10	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3.13
11	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	3.93
12	3	3	5	3	3	3	3	5	3	4	3.20
13	4	5	4	4	4	3	4	5	5	4	3.83
14	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3.66
15	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
16	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
17	4	4	4	3	4	4	3	3	4	3	3.66
18	3	4	4	4	3	3	3	4	4	4	3.86
19	2	4	3	2	3	3	3	2	3	3	2.83
20	5	5	3	4	3	5	5	4	4	4	3.20
21	4	4	4	3	3	4	3	3	4	4	3.53
22	4	4	5	5	4	4	3	2	4	3	3.36
23	5	4	5	4	4	3	4	3	3	3	3.36
24	3	3	4	4	3	3	3	3	3	4	3.06
25	3	5	3	2	2	4	4	4	4	3	3.36
26	4	3	4	3	4	4	3	3	4	4	3.13
27	5	3	4	4	3	3	3	4	3	3	3.10
28	4	5	4	3	4	3	4	3	5	3	3.33
29	5	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	3.66
30	3	4	4	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3.36

Table 6.10 Response Related to Impact of Risk Assessment on Project Success Criteria

No. of Respondent	Well Planned Project Schedule	Compliance with Safety Health and Environmental Standards	Project with in the Estimated Budget	Well assured Financial and Economic Provisions	Provision made for Force Majeure Situation	Compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements	Well - structured Organizational Management	No issue in Contractual Arrangement	Compliance with the Quality Standards	Compliance with Technical Design Requirements	Mean Response on Project Success
1	4	4	4	4	3	4	3	3	3	4	3.63
2	5	5	4	3	5	4	5	4	4	5	4.20
3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3.73
4	4	4	3	4	4	3	4	3	5	4	3.73
5	5	4	4	4	4	4	5	4	5	5	4.03
6	4	4	3	4	3	3	4	3	3	4	3.50
7	4	4	2	3	3	2	3	2	3	4	3.23
8	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	2.96
9	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5.00
10	3	3	3	4	3	3	3	4	3	3	3.13
11	4	4	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3.93
12	3	2	5	2	3	3	3	2	3	3	3.20
13	4	4	3	3	4	2	4	3	3	3	3.83
14	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3.66
15	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
16	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
17	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	3	3	4	3.66
18	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	3.86
19	3	3	2	2	2	3	3	2	3	4	2.83
20	3	3	3	2	3	2	2	2	2	2	3.20
21	4	4	5	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3.53
22	4	5	4	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	3.36
23	3	4	5	2	4	2	2	2	4	3	3.36
24	3	3	5	2	3	3	3	3	2	2	3.06
25	4	4	5	3	3	3	2	2	3	3	3.36
26	5	3	5	4	3	2	2	2	3	2	3.13
27	4	4	4	2	4	2	3	2	3	3	3.10
28	3	4	4	2	3	2	2	3	4	3	3.33
29	4	4	5	3	3	4	3	4	4	4	3.66
30	4	3	5	3	3	4	3	3	3	3	3.36

Table 6.11 Response Related to Impact of Risk Response on Project Success Criteria

No . of Response	Well Planned Project Schedule	Compliance with Safety Health and Environmental Standards	Project within the Estimated Budget	Well assured Financial and Economic Provisions	Provision made for Force Majeure Situation	Compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements	Well - structured Organizational Management	No issue in Contractual Arrangement	Compliance with the Quality Standards	Compliance with Technical Design Requirements	Mean Response on Project Success
1	5	3	5	4	3	3	3	3	4	4	3.63
2	5	4	4	5	5	4	4	3	4	4	4.20
3	4	4	3	3	4	4	4	3	3	4	3.73
4	4	3	3	4	4	3	4	3	4	4	3.73
5	3	4	5	4	3	3	3	3	3	3	4.03
6	3	4	4	3	3	3	4	4	3	4	3.50
7	2	3	3	3	3	4	4	3	3	4	3.23
8	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	3	2.96
9	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5.00
10	3	4	3	3	4	3	3	3	3	3	3.13
11	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	3	3.93
12	4	3	3	3	3	3	3	4	3	3	3.20
13	5	4	3	3	4	5	5	3	4	4	3.83
14	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3.66
15	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
16	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
17	4	4	4	3	3	4	4	4	3	4	3.66
18	4	4	4	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	3.86
19	2	2	3	3	4	3	4	4	2	3	2.83
20	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3.20
21	3	4	5	4	3	4	3	3	4	3	3.53
22	4	3	3	4	3	3	2	2	3	3	3.36
23	3	3	4	3	3	3	3	3	4	3	3.36
24	4	4	3	3	2	3	3	4	2	2	3.06
25	4	4	5	4	2	3	3	4	4	2	3.36
26	3	3	3	2	3	3	2	2	3	3	3.13
27	3	3	4	3	3	2	2	3	2	2	3.10
28	3	4	5	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	3.33
29	3	3	5	3	2	4	3	2	4	3	3.66
30	4	4	4	3	3	4	3	3	4	3	3.36

**APPENDIX V
HYPOTHESIS ANALYSIS**

1. Ha1-1: There is impact of Risk Identification on well planned project schedule.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Identification on well planned Project Schedule

Table 6.12 Regression to find impact of Risk Identification on well planned project schedule

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.418
R Square	0.175
Adjusted R Square	0.145
Standard Error	0.413
Observations	30

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	1.012	1.012	5.927	0.022
Residual	28	4.780	0.171		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	2.670	0.370	7.220	0.000	1.913	3.428
X Variable 1	0.228	0.094	2.435	0.022	0.036	0.420

The Examined (F) value was equal to (5.927) with possibility value (0.022) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Identification on well planned Project Schedule.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Identification on well planned Project Schedule.

2. Ha1-2: There is impact of Risk Identification on compliance with Safety, Health and Environmental Standards.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Identification on compliance with Safety, Health and Environmental Standards.

Table 6.13 Regression to find impact of Risk Identification on compliance with Safety, Health and Environmental Standards

<i>Regression Statistics</i>						
Multiple R		0.403				
R Square		0.162				
Adjusted R Square		0.132				
Standard Error		0.416				
Observations		30				

<i>ANOVA</i>					
	<i>Df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	0.940	0.940	5.425	0.027
Residual	28	4.852	0.173		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	2.530	0.445	5.685	0.000	1.619	3.442
X Variable 1	0.264	0.113	2.329	0.027	0.032	0.497

The Examined (F) value was equal to (5.425) with possibility value (0.027) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Identification on compliance with Safety, Health and Environmental Standards.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Identification on compliance with Safety, Health and Environmental Standards.

3. Ha1-3: There is impact of Risk Identification on Project within the Estimated Budget.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Identification on Project within the Estimated Budget

Table 6.14 Regression to find impact of Risk Identification on Project within the Estimated Budget

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.249
R Square	0.062
Adjusted R Square	0.029
Standard Error	0.440

Observations 30

ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	0.359	0.359	1.852	0.184
Residual	28	5.432	0.194		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	2.896	0.489	5.926	0.000	1.895	3.897
X Variable 1	0.168	0.124	1.361	0.184	-0.085	0.421

The Examined (F) value was equal to (1.852) with possibility value (0.184) and it is higher than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is no significant impact of Risk Identification on Project within the Estimated Budget.

So hypothesis was rejected:

There is no impact of Risk Identification on Project within the Estimated Budget.

4. Ha1-4: There is impact of Risk Identification on well assured Financial and Economic Provisions.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Identification on well assured Financial and Economic Provisions

Table 6.15 Regression to find impact of Risk Identification on well assured Financial and Economic Provisions

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.513
R Square	0.263
Adjusted R Square	0.237
Standard Error	0.390
Observations	30

ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	1.526	1.526	10.016	0.004
Residual	28	4.266	0.152		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	2.442	0.358	6.825	0.000	1.709	3.175
X Variable 1	0.314	0.099	3.165	0.004	0.111	0.517

The Examined (F) value was equal to (10.016) with possibility value (0.004) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Identification on well assured Financial and Economic Provisions.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Identification on well assured Financial and Economic Provisions.

5. Ha1-5: There is impact of Risk Identification on Provision made for Force Majeure Situation

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Identification on Provision made for Force Majeure Situation

Table 6.16 Regression to find impact of Risk Identification on Provision made for Force Majeure Situation

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.544
R Square	0.296
Adjusted R Square	0.271
Standard Error	0.382
Observations	30

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	1.713	1.713	11.760	0.002
Residual	28	4.079	0.146		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	2.212	0.397	5.574	0.000	1.399	3.025
X Variable 1	0.387	0.113	3.429	0.002	0.156	0.617

The Examined (F) value was equal to (11.760) with possibility value (0.002) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Identification on Provision made for Force Majeure Situation.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Identification on Provision made for Force Majeure Situation.

6. Ha1-6: There is impact of Risk Identification on compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Identification on compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements.

Table 6.17 Regression to find impact of Risk Identification on compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements

<i>Regression Statistics</i>						
Multiple R		0.513				
R Square		0.263				
Adjusted R Square		0.237				
Standard Error		0.390				
Observations		30				

<i>ANOVA</i>					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	1.523	1.523	9.992	0.004
Residual	28	4.268	0.152		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	2.329	0.393	5.921	0.000	1.523	3.135
X Variable 1	0.340	0.107	3.161	0.004	0.120	0.560

The Examined (F) value was equal to (9.992) with possibility value (0.004) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Identification on compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Identification on compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements.

7. Ha1-7: There is impact of Risk Identification on well-structured Organizational Management.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Identification on well-structured Organizational Management

Table 6.18 Regression to find impact of Risk Identification on well-structured Organizational Management

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.548
R Square	0.300
Adjusted R Square	0.275
Standard Error	0.381

Observations 30

ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	1.736	1.736	11.987	0.002
Residual	28	4.055	0.145		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	2.391	0.343	6.978	0.000	1.689	3.092
X Variable 1	0.335	0.097	3.462	0.002	0.137	0.533

The Examined (F) value was equal to (11.987) with possibility value (0.002) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Identification on well-structured Organizational Management.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Identification on well-structured Organizational Management.

8. Ha1-8: There is impact of Risk Identification on No issue in Contractual Arrangement.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Identification on No issue in Contractual Arrangement

Table 6.19 Regression to find impact of Risk Identification on No issue in Contractual Arrangement

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.512
R Square	0.262
Adjusted R Square	0.236
Standard Error	0.391
Observations	30

ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	1.519	1.519	9.955	0.004
Residual	28	4.273	0.153		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	2.565	0.321	7.994	0.000	1.908	3.222
X Variable 1	0.279	0.089	3.155	0.004	0.098	0.461

The Examined (F) value was equal to (9.955) with possibility value (0.004) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Identification on No issue in Contractual Arrangement.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Identification on No issue in Contractual Arrangement.

9. Ha1-9: There is impact of Risk Identification on compliance with the Quality Standards.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Identification on compliance with the Quality Standards.

Table 6.20 Regression to find impact of Risk Identification on compliance with the Quality Standards

<i>Regression Statistics</i>						
Multiple R						0.639
R Square						0.409
Adjusted R Square						0.387
Standard Error						0.350
Observations						30

ANOVA						
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>	
Regression	1	2.366	2.366	19.344	0.000	
Residual	28	3.425	0.122			
Total	29	5.792				

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	1.985	0.362	5.486	0.000	1.244	2.727
X Variable 1	0.409	0.093	4.398	0.000	0.218	0.599

The Examined (F) value was equal to (19.344) with possibility value (0.000) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Identification on compliance with the Quality Standards.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Identification on compliance with the Quality Standards.

10. Ha1-10: There is impact of Risk identification on compliance with Technical Design Requirements.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Identification on compliance with Technical Design Requirements.

Table 6.21 Regression to find impact of Risk Identification on compliance with Technical Design Requirements

<i>Regression Statistics</i>						
Multiple R		0.598				
R Square		0.357				
Adjusted R Square		0.334				
Standard Error		0.365				
Observations		30				

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	2.068	2.068	15.548	0.000
Residual	28	3.724	0.133		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	1.974	0.406	4.867	0.000	1.143	2.805
X Variable 1	0.434	0.110	3.943	0.000	0.209	0.660

The Examined (F) value was equal to (15.548) with possibility value (0.000) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Identification on compliance with Technical Design Requirements.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Identification on compliance with Technical Design Requirements.

11. Ha2-1: There is impact of Risk Assessment on well planned project schedule.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Assessment on well planned Project Schedule

Table 6.22 Regression to find impact of Risk Assessment on well planned project schedule

<i>Regression Statistics</i>						
Multiple R		0.618				
R Square		0.382				
Adjusted R Square		0.360				
Standard Error		0.357				
Observations		30				

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>

Regression	1	2.214	2.214	17.326	0.000
Residual	28	3.578	0.128		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	1.917	0.398	4.813	0.000	1.101	2.733
X Variable 1	0.427	0.102	4.163	0.000	0.217	0.636

The Examined (F) value was equal to (17.326) with possibility value (0.000) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Assessment on well planned Project Schedule.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Assessment on well planned Project Schedule.

12. Ha2-2: There is impact of Risk Assessment on compliance with Safety, Health and Environmental Standards.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Assessment on compliance with Safety, Health and Environmental Standards.

Table 6.23 Regression to find impact of Risk Assessment on compliance with Safety, Health and Environmental Standards

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.674
R Square	0.454
Adjusted R Square	0.435
Standard Error	0.336
Observations	30

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	2.630	2.630	23.290	0.000
Residual	28	3.162	0.113		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	1.830	0.362	5.052	0.000	1.088	2.571
X Variable 1	0.453	0.094	4.826	0.000	0.261	0.646

The Examined (F) value was equal to (23.290) with possibility value (0.000) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Assessment on compliance with Safety, Health and Environmental Standards.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Assessment on compliance with Safety, Health and Environmental Standards.

13. Ha2-3: There is impact of Risk Assessment on Project within the Estimated Budget.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Assessment on Project within the Estimated Budget

Table 6.24 Regression to find impact of Risk Assessment on Project within the Estimated Budget

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.265
R Square	0.070
Adjusted R Square	0.037
Standard Error	0.439
Observations	30

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	0.406	0.406	2.109	0.158
Residual	28	5.386	0.192		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	3.032	0.367	8.263	0.000	2.280	3.784
X Variable 1	0.130	0.090	1.452	0.158	-0.053	0.313

The Examined (F) value was equal to (2.109) with possibility value (0.158) and it is higher than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is no significant impact of Risk Assessment on Project within the Estimated Budget.

So hypothesis was rejected:

There is no impact of Risk Assessment on Project within the Estimated Budget.

14. Ha2-4: There is impact of Risk Assessment on well assured Financial and Economic Provisions.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Assessment on well assured Financial and Economic Provisions

Table 6.25 Regression to find impact of Risk Assessment on well assured Financial and Economic Provisions

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.664
R Square	0.441
Adjusted R Square	0.421
Standard Error	0.340
Observations	30

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	2.553	2.553	22.075	0.000
Residual	28	3.238	0.116		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	2.434	0.246	9.901	0.000	1.931	2.938
X Variable 1	0.346	0.074	4.698	0.000	0.195	0.496

The Examined (F) value was equal to (22.075) with possibility value (0.000) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Assessment on well assured Financial and Economic Provisions.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Assessment on well assured Financial and Economic Provisions.

15. Ha2-5: There is impact of Risk Assessment on Provision made for Force Majeure Situation

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Assessment on Provision made for Force Majeure Situation

Table 6.26 Regression to find impact of Risk Assessment on Provision made for Force Majeure Situation

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.812
R Square	0.659
Adjusted R Square	0.647
Standard Error	0.265
Observations	30

ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	3.819	3.819	54.194	0.000
Residual	28	1.973	0.070		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	1.691	0.257	6.566	0.000	1.163	2.218
X Variable 1	0.532	0.072	7.362	0.000	0.384	0.680

The Examined (F) value was equal to (54.194) with possibility value (0.000) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Assessment on Provision made for Force Majeure Situation.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Assessment on Provision made for Force Majeure Situation.

16. Ha2-6: There is impact of Risk Assessment on compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Assessment on compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements.

Table 6.27 Regression to find impact of Risk Assessment on compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.690
R Square	0.476
Adjusted R Square	0.457
Standard Error	0.329
Observations	30

ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	2.758	2.758	25.449	0.000
Residual	28	3.034	0.108		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	2.390	0.238	10.045	0.000	1.903	2.878
X Variable 1	0.359	0.071	5.045	0.000	0.213	0.505

The Examined (F) value was equal to (25.449) with possibility value (0.000) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Assessment on compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Assessment on compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements.

17. Ha2-7: There is impact of Risk Assessment on well-structured Organizational Management.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Assessment on well-structured Organizational Management

Table 6.28 Regression to find impact of Risk Assessment on well-structured Organizational Management

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.772
R Square	0.597
Adjusted R Square	0.582
Standard Error	0.289
Observations	30

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	3.455	3.455	41.404	0.000
Residual	28	2.337	0.083		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	2.246	0.210	10.713	0.000	1.817	2.676
X Variable 1	0.388	0.060	6.435	0.000	0.264	0.511

The Examined (F) value was equal to (41.404) with possibility value (0.000) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Assessment on well-structured Organizational Management.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Assessment on well-structured Organizational Management.

18. Ha2-8: There is impact of Risk Assessment on No issue in Contractual Arrangement.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Assessment on No issue in Contractual Arrangement

Table 6.29 Regression to find impact of Risk Assessment on No issue in Contractual Arrangement

<i>Regression Statistics</i>						
Multiple R		0.770				
R Square		0.592				
Adjusted R Square		0.578				
Standard Error		0.290				
Observations		30				

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	3.431	3.431	40.693	0.000
Residual	28	2.361	0.084		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	2.299	0.203	11.305	0.000	1.883	2.716
X Variable 1	0.400	0.063	6.379	0.000	0.271	0.528

The Examined (F) value was equal to (40.693) with possibility value (0.000) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Assessment on No issue in Contractual Arrangement.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Assessment on No issue in Contractual Arrangement.

19. Ha2-9: There is impact of Risk Assessment on compliance with the Quality Standards.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Assessment on compliance with the Quality Standards.

Table 6.30 Regression to find impact of Risk Assessment on compliance with the Quality Standards

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.722
R Square	0.521
Adjusted R Square	0.504
Standard Error	0.315
Observations	30

ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	3.019	3.019	30.493	0.000
Residual	28	2.772	0.099		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	2.111	0.267	7.898	0.000	1.563	2.658
X Variable 1	0.416	0.075	5.522	0.000	0.262	0.570

The Examined (F) value was equal to (30.493) with possibility value (0.000) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Assessment on compliance with the Quality Standards.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Assessment on compliance with the Quality Standards.

20. Ha2-10: There is impact of Risk Assessment on compliance with Technical Design Requirements.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Assessment on compliance with Technical Design Requirements.

Table 6.31 Regression to find impact of Risk Assessment on compliance with Technical Design Requirements

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.676
R Square	0.458
Adjusted R Square	0.438
Standard Error	0.335
Observations	30

ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	2.650	2.650	23.614	0.000
Residual	28	3.142	0.112		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	2.334	0.258	9.047	0.000	1.806	2.863
X Variable 1	0.351	0.072	4.859	0.000	0.203	0.499

The Examined (F) value was equal to (23.614) with possibility value (0.000) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Assessment on compliance with Technical Design Requirements.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Assessment on compliance with Technical Design Requirements.

21. Ha3-1: There is impact of Risk Response on well planned project schedule.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Response on well planned Project Schedule

Table 6.32 Regression to find impact of Risk Response on well planned project schedule

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.638
R Square	0.406
Adjusted R Square	0.385
Standard Error	0.350
Observations	30

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	2.354	2.354	19.175	0.000
Residual	28	3.438	0.123		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	2.272	0.299	7.593	0.000	1.659	2.885
X Variable 1	0.352	0.080	4.379	0.000	0.187	0.517

The Examined (F) value was equal to (19.175) with possibility value (0.000) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Response on well planned Project Schedule.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Response on well planned Project Schedule.

22. Ha3-2: There is impact of Risk Response on compliance with Safety, Health and Environmental Standards.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Response on compliance with Safety, Health and Environmental Standards.

Table 6.33 Regression to find impact of Risk Response on compliance with Safety, Health and Environmental Standards

<i>Regression Statistics</i>						
Multiple R		0.671				
R Square		0.450				
Adjusted R Square		0.431				
Standard Error		0.337				
Observations		30				

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	2.607	2.607	22.928	0.000
Residual	28	3.184	0.114		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	1.815	0.368	4.933	0.000	1.061	2.569
X Variable 1	0.483	0.101	4.788	0.000	0.276	0.689

The Examined (F) value was equal to (22.928) with possibility value (0.000) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Response on compliance with Safety, Health and Environmental Standards.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Response on compliance with Safety, Health and Environmental Standards.

23. Ha3-3: There is impact of Risk Response on Project within the Estimated Budget.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Response on Project within the Estimated Budget

Table 6.34 Regression to find impact of Risk Response on Project within the Estimated Budget

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.479
R Square	0.229
Adjusted R Square	0.202
Standard Error	0.399
Observations	30

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>

Regression	1	1.327	1.327	8.323	0.007
Residual	28	4.465	0.159		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	2.516	0.366	6.866	0.000	1.765	3.267
X Variable 1	0.270	0.094	2.885	0.007	0.078	0.462

The Examined (F) value was equal to (8.323) with possibility value (0.007) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Response on Project within the Estimated Budget.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Response on Project within the Estimated Budget.

24. Ha3-4: There is impact of Risk Response on well assured Financial and Economic Provisions.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Response on well assured Financial and Economic Provisions

Table 6.35 Regression to find impact of Risk Response on well assured Financial and Economic Provisions

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.751
R Square	0.564
Adjusted R Square	0.548
Standard Error	0.300
Observations	30

ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	3.266	3.266	36.210	0.000
Residual	28	2.526	0.090		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	1.845	0.289	6.384	0.000	1.253	2.437
X Variable 1	0.492	0.082	6.017	0.000	0.325	0.660

The Examined (F) value was equal to (36.210) with possibility value (0.000) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Response on well assured Financial and Economic Provisions.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Response on well assured Financial and Economic Provisions.

25. Ha3-5: There is impact of Risk Response on Provision made for Force Majeure Situation

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Response on Provision made for Force Majeure Situation

Table 6.36 Regression to find impact of Risk Response on Provision made for Force Majeure Situation

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.600
R Square	0.360
Adjusted R Square	0.337
Standard Error	0.364
Observations	30

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	2.085	2.085	15.752	0.000
Residual	28	3.706	0.132		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	2.372	0.305	7.784	0.000	1.748	2.996
X Variable 1	0.351	0.088	3.969	0.000	0.170	0.532

The Examined (F) value was equal to (15.752) with possibility value (0.000) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Response on Provision made for Force Majeure Situation.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Response on Provision made for Force Majeure Situation.

26. Ha3-6: There is impact of Risk Response on compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Response on compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements.

Table 6.37 Regression to find impact of Risk Response on compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements

<i>Regression Statistics</i>						
Multiple R		0.677				
R Square		0.458				
Adjusted R Square		0.439				
Standard Error		0.335				
Observations		30				

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	2.655	2.655	23.699	0.000
Residual	28	3.137	0.112		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	2.088	0.307	6.805	0.000	1.460	2.717
X Variable 1	0.414	0.085	4.868	0.000	0.240	0.589

The Examined (F) value was equal to (23.699) with possibility value (0.000) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Response on compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Response on compliance with Political, Legal and Social Requirements.

27. Ha3-7: There is impact of Risk Response on well-structured Organizational Management.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Response on well-structured Organizational Management

Table 6.38 Regression to find impact of Risk Response on well-structured Organizational Management

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.621
R Square	0.385
Adjusted R Square	0.363
Standard Error	0.357
Observations	30

ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	2.231	2.231	17.539	0.000
Residual	28	3.561	0.127		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	2.322	0.301	7.714	0.000	1.705	2.938
X Variable 1	0.358	0.086	4.188	0.000	0.183	0.534

The Examined (F) value was equal to (17.539) with possibility value (0.000) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Response on well-structured Organizational Management.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Response on well-structured Organizational Management.

28. Ha3-8: There is impact of Risk Response on No issue in Contractual Arrangement.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Response on No issue in Contractual Arrangement

Table 6.39 Regression to find impact of Risk Response on No issue in Contractual Arrangement

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.368
R Square	0.135
Adjusted R Square	0.104
Standard Error	0.423
Observations	30

ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	0.784	0.784	4.381	0.046
Residual	28	5.008	0.179		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	2.782	0.376	7.395	0.000	2.011	3.552
X Variable 1	0.231	0.110	2.093	0.046	0.005	0.457

The Examined (F) value was equal to (4.381) with possibility value (0.000) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Response on No issue in Contractual Arrangement.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Response on No issue in Contractual Arrangement.

29. Ha3-9: There is impact of Risk Response on compliance with the Quality Standards.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Response on compliance with the Quality Standards.

Table 6.40 Regression to find impact of Risk Response on compliance with the Quality Standards

<i>Regression Statistics</i>						
Multiple R						0.708
R Square						0.501
Adjusted R Square						0.483
Standard Error						0.321
Observations						30

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	2.903	2.903	28.142	0.000
Residual	28	2.888	0.103		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	2.230	0.256	8.710	0.000	1.705	2.754
X Variable 1	0.389	0.073	5.305	0.000	0.239	0.539

The Examined (F) value was equal to (28.142) with possibility value (0.000) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Response on compliance with the Quality Standards.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Response on compliance with the Quality Standards.

30. Ha3-10: There is impact of Risk Response on compliance with Technical Design Requirements.

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if impact of Risk Response on compliance with Technical Design Requirements.

Table 6.41 Regression to find impact of Risk Response on compliance with Technical Design Requirements

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.678
R Square	0.460
Adjusted R Square	0.440
Standard Error	0.334
Observations	30

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	2.661	2.661	23.805	0.000
Residual	28	3.130	0.112		
Total	29	5.792			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	2.220	0.280	7.936	0.000	1.647	2.793
X Variable 1	0.400	0.082	4.879	0.000	0.232	0.567

The Examined (F) value was equal to (23.805) with possibility value (0.000) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05) which shows that there is a significant impact of Risk Response on compliance with Technical Design Requirements.

So hypothesis was accepted:

There is an impact of Risk Response on compliance with Technical Design Requirements.